

D6.3

Business Continuity Models, Adaptation Strategies Standard Response Procedures

Project name

Deployment and Assessment of Predictive modelling, environmentally sustainable and emerging digital technologies and tools for improving the resilience of IWW against Climate change and other extremes

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List of definitions, abbreviations, and acronyms

This section provides the meanings of abbreviations and acronyms used multiple times throughout the document. Terms appearing only once are only defined at their first appearance and are not listed here.

Abbreviation	Meaning
BC	Business Continuity
BCA	Business Continuity Assessment
BCE	Business Continuity Engine
BCP	Business Continuity Plan
BCS	Business Continuity Strategy
BOM	Business Operation Model
CC	Climate Change
DSS	Decision Support System
Dx.x	Deliverable x.x
IMS	Incident Management System
IWAT	IWW Assessment Tool
IWW	Inland WaterWays
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
Mx	Month x
n.d.	no date
RAE	Risk Assessment Engine
SOP	Standard Operating Procedure
SRP	Standard Response Procedure
STO	Scientific and Technical Objective
Tx.x	Task x.x
WP	Work Package

Executive Summary

The PLOTO project aims to increase the resilience of the Inland WaterWays (IWW) and the connected hinterland infrastructure, thus ensuring reliable network availability under unfavourable conditions, such as extreme weather, accidents, and other kinds of hazards. PLOTO's main target is to combine downscaled Climate Change (CC) scenarios (applied to IWW infrastructure) with simulation tools and actual data, to provide the relevant authorities and their operators with an integrated tool able to support more effective management of their infrastructure at strategic and operational levels. The PLOTO integrated platform and its tools are validated in three case studies in Belgium, Romania, and Hungary.

To summarise, D6.3 aims to:

- Identify key **natural and man-made hazards affecting IWW ports**, underline the **amplifying role of CC**, and **introduce a structured approach for managing emergencies and recovery through Standard Response Procedures (SRPs)/Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs), Adaptation Strategies, and Business Continuity Strategies (BCSs)** to enhance operational resilience, preparedness, and crisis management.
- Present the **SRPs/SOPs framework developed within PLOTO**, detailing **hazard-specific responses, operational thresholds, real-world practices** derived from **end-user engagement and surveys**, and the challenges identified throughout the process.
- Explore the **Adaptation Strategies framework for IWW ports**, distinguishing proactive and reactive management approaches, and **outlining proactive risk management techniques**, such as avoidance, sharing, reduction, abatement, and transfer, all implemented through Physical, Social, and Institutional measures to enhance climate resilience, operational continuity, and long-term sustainability of port infrastructure.
- Detail the **BCSs framework as a sector-wide approach** to strengthen resilience of IWW and hinterland infrastructure against hazards, outlining three key strategies: Do-Nothing (BCS0), Business Traffic Redistribution (BCS1), and Insurance (BCS2), and highlighting their roles in maintaining service continuity, reducing economic losses, and enabling rapid recovery through redundancy, adaptability, and financial protection mechanisms.
- Outline the developed detailed **Business Operation Models (BOMs)** for five ports in the Romanian Lower Danube area and the Port of Budapest in Hungary, integrating asset exposure, complex freight flow data, and operational flowcharts. A dedicated software developed within PLOTO, the Business Continuity Engine (BCE), leverages all this data. This quantifies the indirect impacts of hazards, establishing a replicable methodology for operational resilience assessment across European inland ports.
- **Demonstrate the application of PLOTO innovative tools to examine and validate BCSs and Adaptation Strategies through** extensive evaluation of multiple **“what-if” scenarios using the BCE**, within which critical asset-nodes were identified, disruption impacts were quantified, and various proactive, risk-sharing, and insurance-enabled measures were applied. The resulting quantified outcomes illustrate how these analyses can enhance port resilience, maximize Business Continuity (BC), minimize service disruptions, and ensure rapid recovery under extreme events.
- **Report the assessment of the Port of Budapest's hazard vulnerability**, confirming water level fluctuations as the top climate risk, and the recommended targeted resilience measures, including infrastructure upgrades and intelligent traffic management.

1. Introduction

1.1 Project information

The project entitled “**Deployment and assessment of predictive modelling, environmentally sustainable and emerging digital technologies and tools for improving the resilience of IWW against CC and other extremes (PLOTOTO)**” aims at increasing the resilience of the IWW and the connected hinterland infrastructures, especially under adverse conditions, such as extreme weather, accidents, and other hazards. In doing this, downscaled CC scenarios are combined with simulation tools and actual data, to provide operators with an integrated tool able to support more effective management of their infrastructures at strategic and operational levels.

PLOTOTO project consists of the deployment and assessment of predictive modelling, environmentally sustainable and emerging digital technologies, and tools for improving the resilience of IWW against CC and other extremes. An integrated tool is set up to allow relevant authorities to improve the efficiency of their infrastructure management. Six complementary avenues are considered to achieve the integrated tool that will support relevant authorities and their operators for more effective management:

- Measure and use high-resolution modelling data for the determination and assessment of the climatic risk of the selected transport infrastructures and associated expected damages.
- Use existing data from various sources with new types of sensor-generated data (computer vision) to feed the used simulator.
- Utilise tailored weather forecasts (combining seamlessly all available data sources) for specific hot spots, providing real-time early warnings with corresponding impact assessment.
- Develop improved multi-temporal, multi-sensor UAV- and satellite-based observations with robust spectral analysis, computer vision, and machine learning-based assessment for diverse transport infrastructures.
- Design and implement an integrated resilience assessment platform environment as an innovative planning tool that will permit a quantitative resilience assessment through an end-to-end simulation environment, running “what-if” impact/risk/resilience assessment scenarios. The effects of adaptation measures can be investigated by changing the hazard, exposure, and vulnerability input parameters.
- Design and implement a Common Operational Picture, including an enhanced visualisation interface and an Incident Management System.

The PLOTOTO integrated platform and its tools are validated in three case studies in Belgium, Romania, and Hungary.

1.2 Purpose of the deliverable

Deliverable 6.3 (D6.3) “Business Continuity Models, Adaptation Strategies Standard Response Procedures” is one of the deliverables of Work Package 6 (WP6) and is related to tasks: Task 6.2 (T6.2) “Assessing Business Continuity Models and Adaptation Strategies” and T6.3 “Assessing response actions and establishing Standard Response Procedures”.

The following description outlines the individual **technical tasks** conducted within T6.2 and T6.3:

- Development of BOMs for ports in Demonstration Cases A (Romania, 5 ports) and B (Hungary, Budapest, 1 port). This process involved collecting ports' data, such as specialization (freight or passenger hub classification), annual traffic volumes (freight import/export data or passenger numbers), and product-specific traffic flowcharts. [T6.2]
- Encoding BOMs of the ports of Demonstration Case A (Romania) into BCE, a software component that enables Business Continuity Assessment (BCA) and allows the integration of the results into the PLOTO IWW Assessment Tool (IWAT), enabling the visualization of the results by the end-users of the PLOTO platform. [T6.2]
- Examination of Adaptation Strategies framework for the IWW to address CC and natural hazard risks, encompassing proactive risk management techniques implemented through integrated Physical, Social, and Institutional measures for structural and organizational adaptation. [T6.2]
- Examination of alternative BCSs for the IWW and selection of the most appropriate ones in cooperation with the end-users. [T6.2]
- Evaluation of the alternative strategies, both Adaptation and BCSs, by comparison of numerous "what-if" scenarios to assess ways to maximise BC and minimise service disruptions to IWW, focusing on the operation of ports. [T6.2]
- Development of SRPs/SOPs per hazard type, integrating end-user input collected through structured questionnaires, meetings, and workshops within the PLOTO consortium. [T6.3]
- Definition of operational thresholds for SOP activation, based on port-specific indicators (e.g., wind speed, water level, river discharge) identified by consortium partners in Galati, the Albert Canal, and the Freeport of Budapest. [T6.3]
- Implementation of a platform mechanism enabling the activation of response plans guiding the operator in managing and resolving specific disruption scenarios. The mechanism reflects the end users' organizational response structures and operationalizes the SRPs within the PLOTO platform environment. [T6.3]

To summarise, D6.3 aims to:

- a. Identify key natural and man-made hazards affecting IWW ports, underline the amplifying role of CC, and introduce a structured approach for managing emergencies and recovery through SRPs/SOPs, Adaptation Strategies, and BCSs to enhance operational resilience, preparedness, and crisis management.
- b. Present the SRPs/SOPs framework developed within PLOTO, detailing hazard-specific responses, operational thresholds, real-world practices derived from end-user engagement and surveys, and the challenges identified throughout the process.
- c. Explore the Adaptation Strategies framework for IWW ports, distinguishing proactive and reactive management approaches, and outlining proactive risk management techniques, such as avoidance, sharing, reduction, abatement, and transfer, all implemented through Physical, Social, and Institutional measures to enhance climate resilience, operational continuity, and long-term sustainability of port infrastructure.
- d. Detail the BCSs framework as a sector-wide approach to strengthen resilience of IWW and hinterland infrastructure against hazards, outlining three key strategies: Do-Nothing (BCS0), Business Traffic Redistribution (BCS1), and Insurance (BCS2), and highlighting their roles in maintaining service continuity, reducing economic losses, and enabling rapid recovery through redundancy, adaptability, and financial protection mechanisms.

- e. Outline the developed detailed BOMs for five ports in the Romanian Lower Danube area and the Port of Budapest in Hungary, integrating asset exposure, complex freight flow data, and operational flowcharts. A dedicated software developed within PLOTTO, the BCE, leverages all this data. This quantifies the indirect impacts of hazards, establishing a replicable methodology for operational resilience assessment across European inland ports.
- f. Demonstrate the application of PLOTTO innovative tools to examine and validate BCSs and Adaptation Strategies through extensive evaluation of multiple “what-if” scenarios using the BCE, within which critical asset-nodes were identified, disruption impacts were quantified, and various proactive, risk-sharing, and insurance-enabled measures were applied. The resulting quantified outcomes illustrate how these analyses can enhance port resilience, maximize BC, minimize service disruptions, and ensure rapid recovery under extreme events.
- g. Report the assessment of the Port of Budapest’s hazard vulnerability, confirming water level fluctuations as the top climate risk, and the recommended targeted resilience measures, including infrastructure upgrades and intelligent traffic management.

Attainment of the objectives

D6.3 is related to PLOTTO Scientific and Technical Objectives (STOs): STO-1 “To investigate and apply various selected solutions (including technical oriented and nature-based solutions) and assess their performance within the inland water ecosystem using a methodology and framework based on specific indicators, action fields and impact factors” and STO-5: “Improved vulnerability analysis and resilience assessment, including digital winning tools to simulate IWW”. The development of BCSs, adaptation strategies, as well as SRPs aligns with the improvement of the IWW resilience assessment with a focus on ports.

1.3 Intended audience

D6.3 is public and thus, it will be available openly to all stakeholders. These include public authorities, IWW and other hinterland infrastructure owners and operators, researchers, technology providers, as well as decision and policy makers.

The deliverable focuses on presenting IWW end-user needs and requirements related to the design and development of a system that improves the IWW resilience against CC and other extreme events.

1.4 Structure of the deliverable and its relation to other work packages/deliverables

D6.3 has been structured as follows:

- Section 1. Describes PLOTTO’s aim, as well as this document’s purpose, intended audience, and structure.
- Section 2. Describes the methodology followed in this deliverable.
- Section 3. Describes the identified hazards affecting inland ports, as well as the phases of emergency response and recovery following a disruptive event, introducing the key concepts that are further developed in this document.
- Section 4. Describes the SRPs/SOPs framework of PLOTTO through the hazard-specific responses and practices gathered through end-user engagement and questionnaires.
- Section 5. Describes the adaptation strategies that inland ports could employ to tackle risks related to natural hazards and CC.

- Section 6. Describes the proposed alternative BCSs.
- Section 7. Describes the developed inland ports BOMs per PLOTO Demonstration Case.
- Section 8. Describes the analyses and assessments of "what-if" impact scenarios for evaluating the effectiveness of adaptation strategies and BCSs.
- Section 9. Concludes the deliverable by summarising the main outcomes.

The deliverable content primarily builds upon the core outcomes of WP4. Especially, the BOMs developed within T6.2 have been created directly based on the developed Exposure Model, produced in T4.2 and detailed in D4.4 and D4.5. These BOMs serve as input to the BCE, part of the PLOTO Indirect Impact Assessment, whose methodology is described in D4.5. D6.3 presents the data used for this tool as input, and demonstrates its potential broad range of utilizations. Additionally, the BOMs incorporate outputs from the Direct Impact Assessment via the Risk Assessment Engine (RAE, T4.3, D4.5), linking the BCE with predictive models, hazard assessments, and vulnerability analysis tools developed across WP3, WP4, and WP6.

1.5 Key terminology and definitions

This section provides a list of **definitions** for key terms **that have been previously introduced** in other PLOTO deliverables. The terms listed here are not defined within the subsequent sections of this report. The purpose of this glossary is to ensure clarity and consistency by providing a central reference for the established concepts, thereby enhancing the overall **readability** and technical precision of the document.

- **Hazard:** Stressors associated with a threat, whose occurrence may affect the normal activities of people and the integrity and functionality of IWW and non-IWW assets, including, for example, ground shaking for earthquakes or wind action for storms.
- **Exposure model:** A comprehensive list of assets within integrated infrastructure systems, such as ports, that are exposed to hazards like floods or earthquakes. This model includes specific details for each asset, such as geospatial location, structural materials, height, number of stories, area, etc., which are used to quantify the potential consequences through risk and resilience assessments.
- **Port Import (IWW-to-Inland):** Goods *arriving* at the port by vessel, either fluvial (river-based) or maritime (sea-based), and subsequently *departing* from port via inland transportation (e.g., by road or rail). Intermediate operations such as handling, inter-port transfer, and storage are included.
- **Port Export (Inland-to-IWW):** Goods *arriving* at the port from inland origin (e.g., by road or rail) and subsequently *departing* from port via vessel, either fluvial (river-based) or maritime (sea-based). Intermediate operations such as handling, inter-port transfer, and storage are included.
- **Port Transit (Inland-to-Inland):** Goods *arriving* at the port from an inland origin (e.g., by road or rail) and subsequently *departing* from port (again) via inland transportation (i.e., by road or rail) without onward movement by vessel. The port serves as an intermediate hub for handling, storage, consolidation, or modal shift between land-based transport modes.

2. Methodology

D6.3 is linked to tasks: T6.2 “Assessing Business Continuity Models and Adaptation Strategies” (leader: SoReCC, duration: Month 20th to Month 30th (M20-M38)) and T6.3 “Assessing response actions and establishing Standard Response Procedures” (leader: STWS, duration: M24-M38). In more detail, it includes: (a) selecting appropriate BCSs for IWW [T6.2], (b) collecting and analyzing data for inland port BOMs [T6.2], (c) developing a Python-coded software which uses the BOMs data as input and estimates the impact of catastrophic events to organizations’ operations, (d) introducing adaptation strategies framework and BCSs for inland ports, and evaluating them through “what-if” scenarios simulations [T6.2], (d) developing the PLOTO SRPs/SOPs framework, detailing hazard-specific practices gathered through end-user engagement and questionnaires [T6.3], and (e) implementing the mechanism for activating and managing response plans within the platform, enabling the application of SRPs derived from the “what-if” scenario assessments in IWAT. These procedures guide operators through predefined actions for effective and timely response during disruptive events, supporting coordinated decision-making and continuity of operations across involved agencies [T6.3].

Figure 1 presents the WP6 high-level architecture, where the BCA [T6.2] and SRPs [T6.3] are depicted. Figure 1 also illustrates the interconnection of T6.2 and T6.3 with the rest of the modules of WP6. Essentially, BCA receives data from Middleware [T6.4] about the potential damage of assets due to natural hazards and CC and evaluates the BC of the IWW ports. BCA interacts with the IWAT platform [T6.1] to display the results, while receives data for an on-demand analysis of the BC for the “what-if” scenarios. In the figure, the SRPs (T6.3) feed into the Incident Management System (IMS) & Decision Support System (DSS) (T6.7), representing how predefined hazard-specific workflows and response actions are integrated into the operational decision-making environment. This linkage ensures that, during incidents, the IMS/DSS can automatically propose appropriate response strategies and resource deployments, facilitating coordinated and timely crisis management. Through the definition of SRPs directly in the PLOTO platform implemented in T6.3, the system provides an integrated mechanism for activating and executing response plans, linking the BCA outcomes with actionable operational procedures.

Figure 1: WP6 high-level architecture¹

¹ Source: adopted from D2.2

To meet the objectives of D6.3, the contributing partners of T6.2 and T6.3 have cooperated closely and communicated via WP6 coordination meetings, ad-hoc meetings, and dedicated bilateral meetings with the end-users. Technical partners worked towards achieving STO-1 and STO-5 and the relevant Key Performance Indicators (KPIs).

Figure 2 schematically illustrates the time plan and milestones for the work performed on T6.2. The methodology implemented for this task consisted of the following steps:

- 1) Initial development of BOMs for the IWW ports and the subsequent refinement/update.
- 2) Examination of alternative BCSs for the IWW and selection of the most appropriate ones in cooperation with the end users.
- 3) Development of a framework for port adaptation strategies.
- 4) Running of “what-if” scenarios.
- 5) Simulations of numerous hazard scenarios and integration into IWAT, which constitute part of the work done under T4.5, and involves the results of the BOMs analyses.

Figure 2: Time plan and milestones of T6.2

Figure 3 schematically illustrates the time plan and milestones for the work on T6.3. The methodology implemented for this task consisted of the following steps:

- 1) Assessing key hazards affecting the IWW ports.
- 2) End-user engagement and data collection on SRPs, operational thresholds, etc.
- 3) Data assessment and hazard-specific SRP/SOP drafting.
- 4) Finalization of the emergency management framework and integration into PLOTO system.

Figure 3: Time plan and milestones of T6.3

3. Emergency and recovery phases to hazard incidents

3.1 Hazard events and incident types

The IWW port operators encounter numerous challenges stemming from both natural and man-made hazards, as well as the growing impacts of CC. These events and incidents can significantly disrupt port operations, causing financial losses, delays in cargo movement, and safety risks to personnel and infrastructure. Below are some of the primary hazards affecting the IWW ports. It should be taken into consideration that even if not all fall in the scope of PLOTTO, from a Use Case perspective, however, additional hazard types could be embedded within the spectrum of considered operations by following a similar methodological approach.

3.1.1. Natural Hazards

- **Flooding** – Inland ports are particularly vulnerable to flooding due to the rising water levels from heavy rainfall, hurricanes, or storm surges. Excessive flooding can damage the port infrastructure, submerge cargo storage areas, and make navigation unsafe. Additionally, flood-related debris can clog waterways, hinder vessel movement, and require extensive cleanup efforts.
- **Drought and Low Water Levels** – Extended periods of drought can lead to reduced water levels, affecting the navigability of IWW. This can restrict vessel movements, reduce cargo capacity, and necessitate dredging operations to maintain channel depth. Low water levels may also affect cooling systems in industrial facilities reliant on river water.
- **Storms and Extreme Weather** – Severe storms, including tornadoes, hurricanes, and high winds, can damage port facilities, topple cranes, and interrupt loading/unloading operations. Lightning strikes pose risks to personnel and electronic systems. In some cases, storms can cause structural damage to warehouses, leading to cargo loss or spoilage.
- **Ice Formation and Freezing Conditions** – In colder regions, prolonged freezing can obstruct waterways, halt navigation, and damage vessel hulls and port infrastructure. Icebreaking operations may be required to maintain accessibility. Ice accumulation on docks and vessels also poses slip hazards for workers.
- **Erosion and Sedimentation** – Changes in water flow due to climate shifts or extreme weather can cause erosion along riverbanks and sedimentation in channels, requiring frequent dredging and maintenance. Erosion can weaken the structural integrity of port facilities and pose long-term stability risks.
- **Heatwaves and Rising Temperatures** – Excessive heat can affect port workers, degrade perishable goods in storage, and affect the efficiency of machinery and equipment. Prolonged high temperatures may also lead to an increased risk of wildfires in surrounding areas, endangering nearby infrastructure.
- **Seismic Events** – Inland ports in seismically active regions may be at risk of earthquakes, which can cause structural damages to the port infrastructure, disrupt cargo handling operations, and trigger secondary hazards such as landslides or soil liquefaction. Strong seismic activity can compromise bridges, docks, and storage facilities, requiring extensive recovery efforts.

3.1.2. Man-Made Hazards

- Industrial Accidents and Hazardous Material Spills – The transportation of chemicals, fuel, and other hazardous materials increases the risk of spills, leading to environmental contamination, health hazards, and costly cleanup operations. Spills can also affect local drinking water supplies and aquatic ecosystems.
- Collisions and Groundings – Increased vessel traffic in congested waterways raises the likelihood of accidents, including collisions between ships or groundings due to shifting riverbeds. Such incidents can result in delays, structural damage to vessels, and even oil spills.
- Cybersecurity Threats – Digital infrastructure supporting port operations, such as automated scheduling, tracking systems, and cargo management, is vulnerable to cyberattacks, leading to potential operational disruptions and data breaches. Cyber incidents could also affect navigation systems, creating safety hazards for vessels.
- Infrastructure Failures – Aging port infrastructure, including docks, bridges, and locks, can suffer structural failures, require emergency repairs and cause operational bottlenecks. Insufficient maintenance or design flaws can exacerbate these risks, leading to costly restoration projects.
- Terrorism and Security Threats – Ports handling high-value cargo or strategic goods are potential targets for terrorist activities, requiring robust security measures to prevent unauthorized access and attacks. Security incidents can lead to port lockdowns and increased scrutiny of cargo movements.

3.1.3. Climate Change impact on the IWW

Considering the scope of the PLOTTO project, it is widely acknowledged that CC exacerbates many natural hazards faced by inland port operators and waterway transportation networks. Rising global temperatures, increased frequency and intensity of storms, and altered river flows present significant challenges to the efficiency and sustainability of IWW. These changes manifest in the form of fluctuating water levels, more frequent and severe flooding, prolonged droughts, and increased sedimentation, all of which disrupt inland navigation and port operations. Research highlights that ports, including IWW terminals, are particularly vulnerable to climate-induced hazards such as rising water levels, storm surges, and extreme weather events, which can severely affect infrastructure and logistical operations (Becker, 2020). A global risk assessment of ports published in Nature reports that the median port-specific risk (i.e., infrastructure damage + logistic losses) is USD 7.5 billion per year, with ~32 % of that risk attributed to extreme weather events - tropical cyclones (Verschuur et al., 2021). Such financial implications underscore the necessity for IWW operators to develop robust climate adaptation and resilience strategies.

Fluctuations in water levels, whether caused by excessive rainfall or prolonged droughts, pose operational challenges for the IWW transport. For example, the Panama Canal has faced significant disruptions due to persistent droughts, leading to reduced water levels and operational restrictions. In response, authorities have implemented water-saving measures, expanded the canal's watershed, and proposed new dam projects to ensure long-term operational sustainability (Panama Canal Authority, 2024). Similarly, Argentina's Paraná River, a crucial trade artery for grain exports, has experienced near-record low water levels due to severe droughts, forcing ships to reduce cargo loads to avoid running aground (Heath, 2024). These examples highlight the need for adaptive strategies and infrastructure investments to maintain IWW efficiency in the face of climate variability.

To address these challenges, industry guidance documents such as PIANC's CC Adaptation Planning for Ports and IWW offer comprehensive frameworks to help inland port and waterway operators develop resilience strategies. These resources emphasize the importance of integrating climate risk assessments, investing in adaptive infrastructure, and enhancing emergency preparedness to mitigate climate-related disruptions (PIANC, 2020). By proactively adopting such measures, IWW operators can navigate the complexities introduced by CC, ensuring the long-term sustainability, efficiency, and resilience of their operations in an increasingly volatile environmental landscape.

3.2 Emergency and recovery phases

Disruptive events, ranging from minor incidents to major disasters, can significantly affect an organization's operations. Effective response to these events requires a structured approach that addresses both immediate needs and long-term recovery. This deliverable examines the critical process of responding to hazardous events, focusing on the distinct but interconnected phases of:

- A. **Emergency Actions:** immediate actions to prevent further damage (e.g., stopping a fire, leakage of stored liquids, etc.) and
- B. **Recovery Actions:** actions taken *after* stabilization to restore normal operations.

To effectively manage these phases, three key elements are considered in this deliverable:

- 1) **Standard Response Procedures (SRPs) or Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs)**,
- 2) **Adaptation Strategies**, and
- 3) **Business Continuity Strategies (BCSs)**.

The “**Emergency Actions**” phase is handled by utilizing the element of **SRPs/SOPs**. This element addresses the immediate aftermath of an event, focusing on containing the incident and preventing further damage, analogous to "stopping the bleeding" in a medical emergency. Since operators are uniquely familiar with their facilities, they are the ones who can best take care of emergency actions through the implementation of SRPs. These procedures are designed to transition the situation to a state where recovery can begin.

Once the situation is stabilized, the focus shifts to the “**Recovery Actions**” phase, aimed at restoring normal operations. This phase is facilitated and accelerated by the **Business Continuity (BC)**. This provides the long-term management needed for a successful recovery, analogous to managing a patient's recovery after the immediate threat has been addressed ("stopping the bleeding" and then ensuring the patient regains full functionality). This deliverable presents specific approaches to BC, termed **BCSs**.

Within the context of these two phases, the **Adaptation Strategies** are exclusively concerned with the “**Recovery Actions**” phase, which is related to the BC. These strategies provide the necessary resources and tactical adjustments, focusing on how the organisation adjusts and modifies its operations and facilities to adapt to the new circumstances created by the hazardous event. BCSs and Adaptation Strategies are inextricably linked, representing the two sides of the same coin.

In summary, an effective response to disruptive events requires a structured approach that considers both the immediate emergency actions and the long-term recovery actions. SRPs/SOPs are crucial for the immediate containment and stabilization of an event, while BCSs and Adaptation Strategies facilitate and accelerate the restoration of normal operations. **SRPs/SOPs** are presented in **Section 4**, **Adaptation Strategies** in **Section 5**, and **BCS** in **Section 6**. Additionally, the ‘**what-if**’ impact scenarios for evaluation of both Adaptation Strategies and BCS are given in **Section 8**.

4. Standard Response/Operating Procedures in PLOTO

4.1 Questionnaire output: Response to incidents per hazard type

To minimize the impact of hazards on port operations, the port operators implement targeted precautionary measures in accordance with well-defined SOPs. These SOPs are structured to enable swift and effective incident response, ensuring BC while mitigating potential risks. Within the framework of identifying the active SOPs relevant to the PLOTO project, the data collection process was guided and supported by the end-users and informed by the relevant ‘what-if’ scenarios considered by the project. The methodological approach included scheduling dedicated meetings and workshops with the consortium end users to discuss and validate the task outcomes. Additionally, a dedicated online questionnaire was utilized to further support and streamline the data collection process. An indicative extract of this questionnaire is illustrated in Figure 4. Resulting examples of such SOPs per hazard type are given in the following sub-sections.

The screenshot shows a web-based questionnaire interface. At the top, it says 'Ερώτημα 1 από 7'. The main title is 'Questionnaire on Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs) for Inland Waterway Port Operators in Case of Extreme Weather Events'. Below the title is a brief description: 'This questionnaire aims to collect feedback from inland waterway port operators on the Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs) they implement during extreme weather events. The responses will help identify areas for further improvement in terms of overall efficiency.' There are navigation buttons for back, forward, and search. Below this, it says 'Μετά την ερώτηση 1 Συνέχεια στην επόμενη ερώτηση'. The next section is 'Ερώτημα 2 από 7' and contains several input fields: 'General Information' (with a sub-label 'Περιγραφή (προαιρετικό)'), 'Port Name *' (with a sub-label 'Κείμενο σύντομης απάντησης'), 'Country/Region *' (with a sub-label 'Κείμενο σύντομης απάντησης'), and 'Port Type *' with radio button options for 'Cargo Port' and 'Discharge Port'.

Figure 4: Online questionnaire for data collection on SOPs from the PLOTO platform end-users

4.1.1. Flooding response procedures

Flooding response procedures focus on proactive monitoring, preparedness, and recovery to minimize disruption and ensure safety. These include establishing robust flood monitoring systems and early warning mechanisms that leverage hydrological data and weather forecasts; protecting critical infrastructure by elevating key assets, reinforcing dikes, and installing flood barriers where feasible; and implementing operational adjustments such as enhanced water drainage and pumping systems to manage excess water effectively. Comprehensive emergency planning covers evacuation measures and cargo protection strategies to safeguard people and assets during flood events. Following a flood, response efforts prioritize structural assessments, debris removal, and sanitation measures to restore operations swiftly and safely.

4.1.2. Drought and low water level response procedures

Drought and low water level response procedures emphasize continuous monitoring, adaptive operations, and collaborative management to maintain safe navigation and cargo flow. Key measures include conducting regular water depth assessments and updating navigational charts to reflect changing conditions; adjusting vessel loads to prevent grounding in shallow areas; and implementing water conservation practices at reservoirs while coordinating with water authorities to optimize controlled water releases. Additionally, increasing dredging operations is crucial to maintain the navigable depths and ensure uninterrupted transport, minimizing the impact of prolonged low water levels on operational efficiency and safety.

4.1.3. Storms and extreme weather response procedures

Storm response procedures prioritize early detection, preventive measures, and structured recovery to safeguard personnel, assets, and operations. These include continuous monitoring of the meteorological data for timely storm detection; securing vessels, cargo, and loose equipment through proper tie-down procedures; and enforcing operational safety protocols, such as suspending loading and unloading activities when wind speeds exceed established safety thresholds. Clear communication protocols are essential, incorporating storm warning systems and emergency alerts to ensure rapid dissemination of critical information. Following a storm, recovery efforts focus on inspecting infrastructure for damage, restoring power and essential services, and resuming operations in a controlled, phased manner to ensure safety and operational continuity.

4.1.4. Ice formation and freezing condition response procedures

Ice formation and freezing condition response procedures focus on continuous monitoring, infrastructure resilience, and operational adaptability to ensure safe and efficient winter operations. Key measures include deploying temperature and ice thickness monitoring systems to track evolving conditions, arranging icebreaking services to keep shipping lanes open, and winterizing critical infrastructure by insulating pipes and implementing heating solutions. Worker safety is prioritized by providing appropriate cold-weather gear and enforcing anti-slip measures on docks and walkways. Additionally, shipping schedules are adjusted to avoid peak freezing periods, reducing risks and maintaining reliable cargo transport during severe winter conditions.

4.1.5. Erosion and sedimentation response procedures

Conduct periodic sedimentation surveys and channel depth sedimentation and erosion response procedures emphasize proactive monitoring, preventive reinforcement, and timely maintenance to preserve navigability and protect infrastructure. These include conducting regular sedimentation surveys and channel depth assessments to track changes in riverbed conditions; implementing erosion mitigation measures such as shoreline reinforcement, installing retaining walls, and promoting vegetation growth to stabilize riverbanks; and increasing dredging frequency to remove sediment buildup and maintain smooth navigation. In addition, emergency repair measures are promptly undertaken to address critical erosion issues and prevent further structural damage, ensuring the continued safety and reliability of waterway operations.

4.1.6. Heatwaves and rising temperature response procedures

Extreme heat response procedures prioritize workforce safety, cargo integrity, and operational continuity during high-temperature conditions. Measures include providing shaded rest areas, hydration stations, and enforcing mandatory rest breaks to protect workers from heat-related illnesses; enhancing storage facilities with climate control systems and utilizing refrigerated containers for temperature-sensitive cargo; and conducting regular maintenance checks to prevent overheating of port machinery and electrical systems. Operational adjustments, such as shifting work schedules to cooler hours and activating heat emergency response plans, further help mitigate the impact of the extreme heat on personnel, equipment, and overall port efficiency.

4.1.7. Seismic event response procedures

Earthquake response procedures focus on preparedness, infrastructure resilience, and rapid recovery to ensure port safety and operational continuity. These include conducting regular seismic

vulnerability assessments of critical port structures and reinforcing or retrofitting facilities to withstand seismic activity. Comprehensive emergency preparedness involves developing contingency plans with clear evacuation routes and coordinated response protocols, while securing cranes, storage racks, and other equipment helps prevent hazards during earthquakes. Following the seismic events, post-earthquake inspections are conducted to identify structural vulnerabilities and initiate necessary repairs. To maintain BC, redundant communication systems and alternative logistics plans are established, minimizing operational disruption and ensuring a swift return to normal operations.

4.2 Questionnaire output: Thresholds for engaging SOPs

Considering the above, port operators do identify specific threshold values in specific hazard types, for engaging specific SOP's or proceeding to modify the ongoing operational processes. Indicative examples of such values for the cases of end-users within the PLOTTO consortium are presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Indicative thresholds for engaging SOPs per PLOTTO Use Case and hazard type

Port	Operational Changes	Indicative Thresholds
Galati (Romania)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Partial/full suspension • Emergency teams' deployment 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Wind > 60 km/h • Water level > 5–6 m • Earthquake triggers
Albert Canal (Belgium)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Partial suspension • Vessel relocation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • River discharge > 800–1200 m³/s
Freeport of Budapest (Hungary)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Partial suspension • Halt loading operations 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Wind > 40 km/h • Rain/snow affecting visibility

By implementing the procedures in consideration, the IWW port operators can enhance their resilience to natural hazards, minimize operational disruptions, and ensure the safety of both personnel and infrastructure. However, with respect to the effectiveness and operational outcomes of the said SOPs, end-users of the consortium identified several key challenges affecting the effectiveness of port operations during hazard events, including limited coordination among stakeholders, delayed response times, infrastructure vulnerabilities, and communication gaps. To address these issues, they recommended enhancing real-time monitoring during critical events, conducting regular risk assessments alongside updates to SOPs, and strengthening both emergency team preparedness and communication channels with all relevant stakeholders. These measures aim to improve operational resilience and ensure timely, coordinated responses to future incidents.

5. Adaptation Strategies framework

This section provides a general description of the adaptation strategies that ports could employ to tackle risks related to natural hazards and CC.

Adaptation Strategies: A Proactive and Reactive Approach

Adapting critical IWW hinterland infrastructure, such as ports, to hazards and especially to CC is essential for maintaining trade and economic activity. Moreover, economic models demonstrate that CC adaptation strategies can increase port cargo traffic by reducing environmental costs and encouraging greater operational capacity (Jiang et al., 2020).

Currently, there is not a single comprehensive solution for the CC related adaptation strategies and resilience planning specifically tailored to the inland ports. Although a comprehensive guidance with adaptation measures for ports does exist, such as the portfolio of generic and impact-specific measures in the PIANC (2020) framework, it offers a source of ideas, not a definitive set of solutions. Consequently, the prevailing rationale is that inland ports should begin by developing policies and strategies to identify natural hazards and climate related risks and creating scalable action plans that can be implemented progressively over time (PLATINA 3 - D4.1, 2022).

This deliverable distinguishes two conceptual types of adaptation approaches that can be followed: a) **proactive management**, involving a set of measures and actions that act on the causes of a disruptive scenario, and b) **reactive management**, involving a set of measures and actions that reduce the effects of the scenario by providing alternative measures to the ones proposed within the proactive approach. The set of measures and actions foreseen by the different approaches collectively constitute the **adaptation strategies**. These strategies not only protect against the negative impacts of disruptive scenarios but also enhance resilience, ensuring a continuous cycle of port service operations—from the disruption or interruption phase to the “back to normal” state.

Proactive Management

The proactive management approach concerns risk response strategies to prevent risks that can be eliminated and minimize those that are impossible to avoid. This can be categorized into several risk management techniques or tools. The general categories for these techniques have been adopted from Purpura P. P. (2013), with adjustments made to include some of the measures from PIANC (2020) framework.

A. Risk Avoidance:

This is the first technique that can be used to eliminate a risk and its potential effects. This approach focuses on removing the source of risk (e.g., cancelling a product with inherently dangerous manufacturing processes) or making strategic decisions that prevent exposure to hazardous situations (e.g., a retail chain might decide not to open a store in a location with a very high crime rate) (Purpura P. P., 2013).

However, in PLOTTO's ports context, completely avoiding all risks to port infrastructure is unfeasible, as it is not possible to remove all events caused by natural hazards (e.g., eliminating occurrences of hazards such as earthquakes). Moreover, the strategic site selection by choosing locations that are less vulnerable to natural hazards is a reasonable option for new port facilities,

but not to the existing ones examined within PLOT0. Thus, the Risk Avoidance is presented solely in theoretical terms.

B. Risk Sharing:

In general, this technique involves accepting and then sharing the risk and its effects with another party. It also involves collaboration between the parties to implement measures and actions aimed at mitigating the risk.

For ports, risk sharing involves establishing agreements with neighbouring ports to provide mutual support during emergencies. When a port is impacted by a disaster, it can use alternative ports for its operations, effectively distributing the risk and its consequences. Examples include the Delta Program between Rotterdam and Antwerp, and the rerouting shipments after events like the 2011 Japan earthquake and Hurricane Katrina.

Risk sharing effectiveness, and even feasibility, depends on the extent of the impacts a hazard can cause and on the proximity of the ports. When hazard consequences are more localized and not widespread, and ports are geographically close enough to enable functional substitution, risk sharing serves as a key component of proactive management (Itoh and Zhang, 2023). For example, consider two neighbouring ports with overlapping operations, such as handling the same type of product. Following a hazard event (e.g., an earthquake), both ports may experience damage, potentially reducing the functionality of their assets and leading to delays or overflow cargo. Therefore, while prior coordination and agreements on capacity sharing and logistical arrangements are essential, the ability to effectively transfer product operations from one port to the other depends critically on the remaining functional capacity of the receiving port. This means the receiving port must retain enough undamaged and operational assets to handle the redirected cargo flow, even if it has sustained some damage itself.

C. Risk Reduction and Control:

This technique focuses on reducing the probability of a risk to an acceptable level. This involves measures and actions to:

- i. Reduce the exposure of the assets to an existing hazard. This entails physically separating assets from the hazard. For example, constructing flood defences (e.g., levees, seawalls) to protect assets from inundation.
- ii. Control and improve the initial conditions of assets that would significantly increase risk should a hazard occur. This involves enhancing asset resilience through improved design, maintenance, and operational procedures. For instance, repairing damaged structural elements, monitoring steel structures against corrosion, removing dry shrub and bush cover near the highway to reduce fire hazard, improving de-icing and fog procedures through the use of alerts sensors, or taking countermeasures to stabilise the areas affected by landslides.

D. Risk Consequences Abatement:

Risk consequences abatement focuses on reducing the severity of consequences of a hazard event should it occur, rather than preventing or mitigating the event itself or its risk. It involves implementing measures that limit the potential damage, losses, or negative impacts associated with the hazard. This tool acknowledges that some level of risk may be unavoidable, but it aims to

minimize its effects. For example, airbags in vehicles do not prevent accidents, but they reduce the severity of injuries in a collision.

E. Risk Transfer:

Risk transfer mitigates risk by shifting it to another party. Within a risk management framework, this tool should complement, not replace, loss prevention efforts, acting as a final line of defence. Risk transfer is done primarily through insurance policies covering damage to infrastructure, business interruption, and liability. Leasing equipment, rather than owning it, is another method, transferring the risk of obsolescence to the lessor (Purpura P. P., 2013).

In addition to categorizing adaptation through risk management techniques, adaptation measures can also be classified based on their nature, as outlined in the PIANC (2020) report. This framework offers a complementary perspective, focusing on the type of intervention employed. These categories are:

- Physical: These measures involve tangible interventions, encompassing structural, engineered, technological, systems, and service-based solutions. This includes both hard and soft engineering approaches, nature-based solutions, maintenance activities, and the development of new products. Examples within the port context include infrastructure reinforcement, implementation of nature-based solutions, and improved drainage systems.
- Social: These measures focus on people-based interventions, including operational, management, educational, information-related, and behavioural changes. Examples include developing emergency response plans, conducting training on risks, establishing early warning systems, and modifying operational procedures during high-risk periods.
- Institutional: These measures involve changes at the governance, economic, legal, regulatory, policy, and programmatic levels. Examples include developing port-specific adaptation policies, establishing financial incentives for implementing adaptation measures, and integrating CC considerations into port planning regulations.

Effective adaptation requires an integrated approach, wherein each proactive risk management technique is implemented through a combination of Physical, Social, and Institutional measures, as defined by PIANC (2020). For instance, Risk Sharing can be facilitated by Institutional agreements between ports for mutual support, supported by Social measures such as joint training exercises and coordinated emergency response plans. This integrated approach ensures a more robust and resilient port infrastructure by addressing risks from multiple perspectives.

Reactive Management

The reactive management approach focuses on responding to incidents after they occur, with the goal of minimizing their impact and swiftly restoring normal operations. While it employs similar techniques as the proactive approach, it emphasizes alternative solutions tailored to scenarios that have already occurred. These scenarios are typically associated with risks that were previously mitigated through proactive actions and procedures. Reactive solutions are often costly and implemented under pressure.

In the context of the adaptation measures, reactive management is generally less effective, more expensive, and less tailored to long-term climate trends than the proactive strategies. Therefore, this deliverable focuses exclusively on the proactive adaptation measures designed to anticipate and mitigate hazard impacts before they occur, offering a more cost-effective and sustainable path to resilience.

6. Proposed Business Continuity Strategies

6.1 Definition

Businesses are vulnerable to both natural (e.g., earthquakes, floods) and man-made (e.g., cyber-attacks) hazards, which can lead to substantial direct and indirect losses if left unprepared. **Direct losses**, economically, represent the repair or replacement costs of damaged assets (Hallegatte, 2008), while **indirect losses** encompass business interruption, property devaluation, and stock market impacts (Kaushalya et al., 2014). Given that not all hazards can be prevented, building business resilience is crucial for effective risk mitigation.

To enhance business resilience and mitigate the impact of hazard events, the current best practice is the implementation of Business Continuity Plans (BCPs). These plans aim to reduce crisis impact and facilitate a rapid return to normal operations ("Business as Usual"). While standards, like ISO 22301 (ISO 22301, 2019), provide a general guidance for building resilience, each organization must develop a tailored BCP based on its specific characteristics. Key elements include risk identification, corresponding response procedures, and rigorous training and testing—an iterative process of optimization involving methodology development, team training, and plan revision (Cerullo V. and Cerullo M.J., 2004).

However, rather than exploring individual BCPs, which are generally tailored to individual businesses, this deliverable will focus on sector-wide approaches, termed BCSs. These enable businesses within a specific sector to collectively withstand crises, enhancing overall survivability and protecting the wider community's economy. BCSs also provide valuable insights to regional and local authorities, aiding in the identification of critical components of the IWW and hinterland infrastructure, thus prioritizing support for those sectors most in need during pre-event planning and decision-making.

Three BCSs are proposed herein for supporting the economy of "the IWW and hinterland infrastructure" site that is subjected to either CC or non-CC aggravated hazards, these being the: (a) do-nothing, (b) business traffic redistribution, and (c) insurance strategies. The first strategy, namely do-nothing, essentially corresponds to the absence of comprehensive damage/risk mitigation planning, and it will be denoted from this point onwards as BCS0. BCS0 can be used as the benchmark to assess the performance of the remaining two BCSs (BCS1 and BCS2, for b) and c) respectively). A detailed description along with the pros and cons of each strategy is provided in the subsequent sections.

6.2 Business traffic redistribution (BCS1)

General Description of Traffic Redistribution (BCS1) Business Continuity Strategy

The business traffic redistribution (BCS1) is a BCS for mitigating service disruptions (and consequently losses) within an organization by redirecting activities, operations, and resources (business traffic) to alternative business nodes of the same organization. The core idea is to utilize redundancy and adaptability within a network of assets to ensure continuity of services during disruptions caused by facility failures, environmental challenges, or other emergencies. Its applicability varies based on organization size:

- A. Large organizations (multiple physical premises): BCS1 is particularly effective in systems comprising multiple interchangeable physical assets (e.g., branches of a company, industrial facilities, or logistic hubs) that can perform similar functions. Interchangeability requires a comprehensive business plan to secure data integrity and real-time communication among these assets. For businesses requiring in-person activities, assets should be densely placed to facilitate customer redistribution from the disrupted to the non-disrupted branches/premises.
- B. Smaller firms (few physical premises): BCS1 can be applied to smaller firms with few premises through an "in-cast" procedure. This means that if one asset experiences disruptions (e.g., power outage, structural or non-structural damage), critical departments are transferred to non-disrupted premises to maintain serviceability.
- C. Single-asset firms (one physical premise): Even in the case of single-asset firms, BCS1 can be performed by renting additional workplaces to accommodate the critical departments. However, the success of BCS1 in this case depends heavily on the presence of a comprehensive BCP that ensures that such additional workplaces will be available during a disaster and that the personnel of the disrupted departments can be oriented to them without major difficulties.

6.3 Insurance (BCS2)

General Description of Insurance (BCS2) Business Continuity Strategy

Insurance (BCS2) is a proactive BCS that aims to reduce both direct and indirect losses caused by hazard events. By providing financial protection, it ensures that businesses and communities can recover swiftly and effectively from catastrophic events. Two key types of *non-life insurance contracts* are considered herein, namely: **Traditional (Indemnity-Based) Insurance** and **Parametric (Non-Indemnity, Index-Based) Insurance** (Lin and Kwon, 2020).

A. Traditional (Indemnity-Based) Insurance:

Traditional insurance contract operates on the principle of indemnity, whereby the insurer aims to restore the insured to their pre-loss financial position following a covered adverse event (i.e., in PLOTO case a hazard event like earthquake, flood, extreme wind, etc.). In its simplest theoretical form, and assuming a policy with no limits or deductibles, this type of insurance reimburses the insured for the *total value of the loss* incurred due to the hazard event. However, it is important to note that real-world policies usually include limits and deductibles.

The indemnity-based insurance can be activated only after the occurrence of the hazard event and the confirmation of its resulting damages to the insured assets. What's more, in order to claim the indemnity, a representative of the insurance company must conduct the quantification of the loss after the hazard occurrence through an assessment of the damage. This assessment process often leads to delays in claims settlement (e.g., up to six months), which in turn amplifies indirect losses by forcing businesses to shut down and await post-event inspections before commencing repairs.

B. Parametric (Non-Indemnity, Index-Based) Insurance:

Parametric insurance contract provides an alternative in which the insurer agrees to pay a predefined amount once a specific parameter (index) exceeds a contractually defined threshold. Unlike traditional insurance, it does not depend on the quantification of actual losses, but rather on the occurrence of measurable predefined triggers that indicate potential impacts. Such triggers

could be rainfall levels, wind speeds, or seismic activity reaching a certain magnitude. The amount of payment, the parameter, and the third party responsible for verifying that the parameter threshold has been exceeded, must all be specified in the signed contract (NAIC, 2025).

For instance, a logistics company insures its operations against a flood occurrence with a parametric insurance policy. If rainfall levels in the area exceed 200 mm within a 24-hour period, the policy would trigger a payment of €50,000. The verification of the parameter would typically be performed by a national meteorological agency.

In recent years, parametric insurance solutions have gained popularity due to their versatility and rapid claims processing. These contracts can cover a wide range of risks, addressing the needs of individual clients, businesses, and even governments. The efficiency of parametric insurance lies in its ability to disburse payments almost immediately after the triggering event, as it eliminates the need for detailed damage assessments. This immediacy helps mitigate indirect losses by allowing businesses to begin recovery efforts without delays.

Basis Risk

A key determinant of the success of BCS2 is the management of basis risk. It represents the mismatch between the insurance payout and the actual loss incurred, and varies between traditional and parametric insurance approaches.

In Traditional Insurance basis risk is the difference between the actual loss and the indemnification received (Lin and Kwon, 2020). Insurers manage this risk through careful risk underwriting (assessing the likelihood and potential severity of losses) and accurate claim assessment (determining the actual extent of damage).

In the Parametric Insurance, basis risk is the deviation of the pre-agreed payout from the actual loss. This deviation can be: a) positive when the payout exceeds the actual damage or when insureds are unaffected by the triggering event, or b) negative when actual losses exceed the payout or when losses occur from events with intensities below the pre-defined threshold. A real-world example of negative basis risk occurred during the 2015-2016 drought in Malawi. The country had parametric agricultural insurance through the African Risk Capacity, but a shift to a more drought-vulnerable crop (not reflected in the original model) meant that losses were not initially deemed widespread enough to trigger a payout. Following investigation and model recalibration, a payout was eventually made (NAIC, 2025).

Insurance as a Core Component of Business Continuity Strategies

Despite the particularities or differences between traditional and parametric insurance schemes discussed earlier, insurance is always recommended and remains a critical component of BCSs. When widely adopted, it can effectively mitigate severe economic losses, ultimately assisting local businesses to survive the occurrence of a catastrophic event and strengthen the resilience of a community.

7. Business Operation Models for PLOTO inland ports

7.1 Demonstration Case A: Romania

7.1.1. Introduction

Demonstration Case A of the PLOTO project examines six (6) ports located in five (5) Romanian cities: the passenger ports of Sulina, Tulcea, and Isaccea, as well as the freight hubs of Galati and Braila. These ports are located along the Lower Danube, in close proximity to the river’s entry point from the Black Sea (at Sulina), and form part of the Pan-European Corridor VII, which connects the Black Sea to the North Sea via the Rhine–Main–Danube waterway (European Commission – DG Energy & Transport, 2006).

All ports are included in the Exposure Model conducted in T4.2, and separately, BOM data have been collected for them. The BOM is one of the two tools used in PLOTO to carry out Indirect Impact Assessment. This assessment process begins with a Direct Impact Assessment of the assets included in the Exposure Model, which estimates their downtime following a hazard event. These downtime estimates are then used as inputs to the BOM, enabling the evaluation of broader operational consequences.

The following section presents the BOMs data collected from the operators and analyzed for Demonstration Case A.

7.1.2. Port of Sulina

Port Location

The “**Port of Sulina**” is situated at kilometer 0 along the Lower Danube, on the river’s right bank defined in the downstream direction (i.e., toward the Black Sea), and marks the **Danube’s entry point from the Black Sea**. It lies near Romania’s northern border with Ukraine, within the **protected Danube Delta region**. The location and the area (denoted with red colour) of the examined port is given in Figure 5.

Figure 5: Port of Sulina – Location and area (red colour) (source: Google Maps)

Port Multimodal Access and Connectivity

The port’s **water-based access** features both **fluvial (IWW) and maritime (sea) connectivity**. Located along the Lower Danube, it is navigable by fluvial vessels and accessible to maritime traffic entering from the Black Sea.

However, the port's **land-based access** is limited to the **local road connectivity**, with no direct links to national highways or rail infrastructure. Specifically, while local roads exist within Sulina, the city itself has **no direct road or rail connections leading to it**. This lack of external land connections is due to the protected status of the Danube Delta, which prohibits highway and railway construction. As a result, all passenger transport to Sulina is conducted by ship. This lack of land access is further illustrated in Figure 6, which provides a general view of the city and highlights the absence of road or railway connections.

Figure 6: Port of Sulina – General view of the city and the lack of road or railway connection (source: Google Maps)

Port General Operation

The port serves primarily as a **passenger port**, accommodating mainly maritime vessels arriving from or departing to the Black Sea. These vessels typically stop in Sulina for essential formalities such as border control, toll collection, and entry procedures into Romania. The port does not support cargo-handling activities; meaning there is no trans-shipment of cargo between ships, nor any transfer from ships to road or rail networks.

Port Facilities (Assets from Exposure Model [T4.2] and General Information)

The Sulina port is comprised of two main terminals: (a) Terminal 1 for passenger services and (b) Terminal 2 for border control of maritime traffic. Figure 7 presents their locations, designations, and areas (with yellow colour). Each Terminal is comprised of two berths. These four berths, highlighted in red in Figure 7, collectively constitute the port's Exposure Model within the PLOTTO framework.

Figure 7: Port of Sulina – General view of the port, its terminals (yellow colour), and its four berths (red colour) (source: Google Maps)

Traffic Analysis (General)

Terminal 1 facilitates passenger travel to and from other Danube ports upstream, tracking passengers using domestic public transport. However, passengers transported by small private operators and cruise vessels are not monitored. Table 2 presents the number of passenger arrivals and departures at Sulina in 2022.

Table 2: Port of Sulina – Number of passengers at Terminal 1 during 2022

Year	Passengers Arrivals	Passengers Departures
2022	27,733	20,076

Terminal 2 handles border control for maritime vessels entering and exiting the Danube via the Sulina Channel. The number of ships traffic during the period 2019-2024 is provided in Table 3. Ship traffic declined in 2020 and 2021 due to the COVID-19 pandemic, but saw a significant increase in 2022 and 2023 due to the war in Ukraine.

Table 3: Port of Sulina – Number of ships traffic during the period 2019-2024

Month	2019		2020		2021		2022		2023		2024	
	in	out										
January	80	92	86	88	55	62	84	111	115	178	104	160
February	58	84	67	91	45	59	61	78	101	155	133	165
March	92	104	61	73	58	62	102	79	171	237	[-]	[-]
April	76	86	71	87	70	67	166	144	151	204	[-]	[-]
May	73	83	73	76	58	71	202	197	186	290	[-]	[-]
June	73	76	51	60	59	57	193	192	160	251	[-]	[-]
July	82	93	54	61	62	73	189	208	148	222	[-]	[-]
August	92	94	47	50	84	92	141	229	122	268	[-]	[-]
September	117	118	68	62	101	111	137	193	108	195	[-]	[-]
October	92	105	75	80	95	123	140	181	149	254	[-]	[-]
November	88	95	59	62	70	93	114	184	104	209	[-]	[-]

Month	2019		2020		2021		2022		2023		2024	
	in	out	in	out	in	out	in	out	in	out	in	out
December	81	97	68	77	96	99	135	188	117	194	[-]	[-]
Total	1,004	1,127	780	867	833	969	1,664	1,984	1,638	2,657	237	325
	2131		1647		1822		3648		4289		562	

Legend: a) in: vessels to Sulina Canal and b) out: vessels out of Sulina Canal

Broader/Aggregated Categories of Products/Services for the Purposes of the BOM Analysis

For the BOM analysis, passengers and vehicles are considered the port's "products/services" categories and are further distinguished by import and export data, as shown in Table 4.

Table 4: Port of Sulina – Categories, import/export status, and mapping to model identifiers

Services Category	Import/Export	Model Name	Model ID
Passengers transportation	Import	Pass I	0
	Export	Pass E	2
Vehicles transportation	Import	Veh I	1
	Export	Veh E	3

Port Operation Flowchart (general)

Figure 8 depicts the general port operation flowchart for both passengers and vehicles.

Figure 8: Port of Sulina – Port operation flowchart (general)

Port Operation Flowchart for Passengers

Figure 9 depicts the more specific port operation flowchart for passengers. As sea transport is the main way to travel to and from Sulina town, no seasonality will be considered.

Figure 9: Port of Sulina – Port operation flowchart / Handling of passengers

Port Operation Flowchart for Vehicles

Figure 10 depicts the more specific port operation flowchart for vehicles. Sulina is the main entrance and exit to and from the Danube to the Black Sea, and no seasonality effect will be considered.

Figure 10: Port of Sulina – Port operation flowchart / Handling of vehicles

Information About Past Incidents

The Sulina Channel entrance has experienced closures due to unfavourable weather conditions, as follows: 2018: 26 days, 2019: 37 days, 2020: 28 days, 2021: 30 days, 2022: 29 days, 2023: 31 days, and 2024 (January 7 to February 26): 10 days. Two notable navigation incidents have occurred:

October 7, 2014: The maritime vessel *FORTUNA S* (Moldova flag, IMO 7016383) struck the southern breakwater near Hm 78 1/3, approximately 40 meters from the cap. The vessel, loaded with 2,659 tonnes of salt from Badırma, Turkey, and destined for Galați, was oriented roughly parallel to the breakwater axis. Weather conditions included E-NE wind (force 5-6), sea level 5, and good visibility. The *FORTUNA S* had a GRT of 2,135, TRN of 1,188, DW of 3,433, draft of 6.50 m, length of 81.64 m, and width of 14.28 m.

March 7, 2013: The *M/V M. IZMIR* (Malta flag, IMO 9008079) ran aground on the axis of the south pier between Hm 77+30 and Hm 77+90. The vessel, also loaded with salt from Badırma, Turkey, and

destined for Galați, was subsequently scuttled around 19:30 following intervention by AFDJ tugs *Gheorghieni 2* and *Sulina 3*. Weather conditions included SSE wind (force 5), sea level 5, good visibility, and a strong current on the Sulina Channel. The *M/V M. IZMIR* had a GRT of 4,902, TRN of 2,196, DW of 6,624, draft of 4.20 m, length of 111.60 m, and width of 18.00 m.

7.1.3. Port of Tulcea

Port Location

The “**Port of Tulcea**” is situated at kilometer 71 along the Lower Danube, on the river’s right bank defined in the downstream direction (i.e., toward the Black Sea). Figure 11 depicts the port’s location in the city.

Figure 11: Port of Tulcea – Port’s location (source: Google Maps)

Port Multimodal Access and Connectivity

The port’s **water-based access** features both **fluvial (IWW)** and **maritime (sea) connectivity**. Located along the Lower Danube, it is navigable by fluvial vessels and accessible to maritime traffic entering from the Black Sea.

The port’s **land-based access** includes **local roads**, **national road connections**, and **direct railway connectivity**. Specifically, it is connected to Tulcea’s local road network and linked to the national road system via routes leading into the city, as shown in Figure 12. Additionally, a train station is conveniently located next to the port’s area and is visible in Figure 14 (labeled “Tulcea Oras”).

Figure 12: Port of Tulcea – Port linkage with inland roads that connect to Tulcea (source: Google Maps)

Port General Operation

The port functions primarily as a **passenger and tourist port** under the administration of the Tulcea County Council, and it serves as the point of **origin for all routes into the Danube Delta**. It facilitates both domestic and international transport. The examined port within PLOTO does not accommodate freight operations or ship-to-ship trans-shipments.

Owing to its multimodal connectivity, the port enables multimodal transport operations, supporting the transfer of passengers between inland modes (road and rail) and waterborne modes (fluvial transport along the Danube), and vice versa.

Port Facilities (Assets from Exposure Model [T4.2] and General Information)

The port features a single building with mixed usage, including a passenger terminal, port administration, and commercial areas. Two floating docks, each connected by a pedestrian bridge, facilitate boarding and disembarking for passengers. These assets together make up Terminal 1. However, within the PLOTO framework, only the passenger terminal building is considered part of the port's Exposure Model. Figure 13 depicts the general view of the examined port, while Figure 14 depicts the area of the building and the area of boarding and disembarking.

Figure 13: Port of Tulcea – General view of the examined port (source: Google Maps)

Figure 14: Port of Tulcea – Areas of the terminal building and boarding and disembarking of passengers, and the adjacent train station (denoted as “Tulcea Oras”) (source: Google Maps)

Traffic Analysis (General)

The number of passengers for the domestic and international transport for both arrivals (import) and departures (export) during 2023 is provided in Table 5.

Table 5: Port of Tulcea – Number of passengers during 2023

Traffic flow / No. of passengers	Arrivals (import)	Departures (export)	Total [No.]	Total [%]
Domestic (public)	47,107	49,856	96,963	37
Domestic (private)	80,839	84,836	165,675	64

Traffic flow / No. of passengers	Arrivals (import)	Departures (export)	Total [No.]	Total [%]
Domestic (total = public + private)	127,946	134,692	262,638	91
International	12,563	12,562	25,125	9
Total (Domestic + International)	147,254	140,509	287,763	100
Arrivals: from Danube ports to Tulcea; Departures: from Tulcea to Danube ports				

Broader/Aggregated Categories of Products/Services for the Purposes of the BOM Analysis

For the BOM analysis, passengers are considered the port's "product" categories and are further distinguished by import and export data, as shown in Table 6.

Table 6: Port of Tulcea – Categories, import/export status, and mapping to model identifiers

Services Category	Import/Export	Model Name	Model ID
Passengers transportation	Import	Pass I	0
	Export	Pass E	1

Port Operation Flowchart (general)

Figure 15 presents the general port operation flowchart for passengers.

Figure 15: Port of Tulcea – Port operation flowchart (general)

Port Operation Flowchart for Passengers

Figure 16 presents the more specific port operation flowchart for passengers. No seasonality is considered.

Figure 16: Port of Tulcea – Port operation flowchart / Handling of passengers

Information About Past Incidents

Terminal 1 (Passenger Port) has experienced operational delays in the past due to icing.

7.1.4. Port of Isaccea

Port Location

The “**Port of Isaccea**” is situated at kilometer 103.7 along the Lower Danube, on the river’s right bank defined in the downstream direction (toward the Black Sea). Figure 17 illustrates the port’s location in the city.

Port Multimodal Access and Connectivity

The port’s **water-based access** is primarily **fluvial (IWW)**, facilitated by a direct ferry-boat connection to the **Port of Orlivka**, situated **on the opposite bank of the Danube**—specifically, on the left bank defined in the downstream direction (i.e., toward the Black Sea)—on the Ukrainian side. The two ports lie approximately **900 meters apart** (Danube Commission, 2022), with a crossing time of up to 10 minutes (Ferry Complex Orlivka–Isaccea, Official Website, 2025). Due to this close proximity, these two ports form a binational ferry corridor that supports the daily cross-border movement of both passengers and vehicles. In addition, following infrastructure modernization completed in 2022, the Port of Isaccea also supports now **maritime connectivity**, including access for sea-going cargo vessels alongside inland waterway traffic.

The port’s **land-based access** includes both **local** and **national road** connections. The port area is served by local roads within Isaccea, which connect directly to Romania’s national highway DN 22, part of the European route E 87. This corridor runs parallel to the Danube and links Isaccea to major towns such as Tulcea, Brăila, and beyond, integrating the port into the broader European road network. There is no railway station in Isaccea, and as such, the port is not directly served by rail infrastructure. The nearest railway connection is located in Tulcea, approximately 35 km east of Isaccea by road.

The link between the ports and the proximity to adjacent roads are illustrated in Figure 17.

Figure 17: Port of Isaccea – Inland port connection and fluvial connection between the ports of Isaccea and Orlivka (source: Google Maps)

Port General Operation

The port functions as a **ferry terminal** (Danube Commission, 2022) and **passenger port**, primarily facilitating cross-border traffic between Romania and Ukraine. This connection is enabled via the binational ferry corridor of approximately 900 meters, with operations running 24/7. During daytime hours (08:00–20:00), two ferries operate continuously, departing from each shore approximately every 30–40 minutes. At night (20:00–08:00), a single ferry operates, departing about once per hour (Ferry Complex Orlivka–Isaccea, Official Website, 2025).

The Isaccea port operates under a mixed public-private model. The state-owned Maritime Danube Ports Administration administers the port’s infrastructure. The ferry service connecting Isaccea to Orlivka, Ukraine, is operated by two private companies—one Romanian and one Ukrainian—using **vessels capable of transporting both passengers and vehicles simultaneously** (Danube Commission, 2022).

Owing to its multimodal connectivity, the port enables multimodal transport operations, supporting the transfer of passengers and vehicles (e.g., cars, trucks, or buses) arriving via inland road transport and continuing their journey via fluvial ferry transport to Orlivka in Ukraine, and vice versa.

Notably, a newly constructed berth now allows accommodation of both inland and maritime **freight vessels**, indicating the port’s potential for future expansion beyond its current passenger and vehicle transit functions. However, no freight volume is available within PLOTO data. Therefore, **for the Port of Isaccea no cargo operations will be examined in this project.**

Port Facilities (Assets from Exposure Model [T4.2] and General Information)

The port’s facilities include a berth connected by a bridge to the port’s land area, serving as the boarding and disembarking point for both vehicles (cars, trucks, buses) and passengers. Within the port area, there is a variety of structural types, **primarily isobox units and single-storey steel portal frame structures**. The PLOTO Exposure Model includes the following infrastructure components: (a) a single-storey L-shaped masonry building, (b) a single-storey isobox-type building, and (c) three (3) single-storey steel portal frame structures, each of which shelters multiple smaller isobox units. The steel portal frame structures with the isobox-units function as customs and border control terminals. Figure 18 depicts the general view of the examined port with its structures.

Figure 18: Port of Isaccea – General view of the examined port (source: Google Maps)

Due to the complexity of modeling, the detailed operational routes for handling passengers and vehicles within the individual structures identified in the Exposure Model, **the port area is treated as a single terminal** for the purposes of BOM analysis, as illustrated in Figure 19. For the same reason, this single terminal is **conceptually divided into two terminal components to distinguish** between the operations of: (a) **Passenger handling**, and (b) **Vehicle handling**. Although these components occupy the same physical area, they are functionally separated for modeling purposes (Table 7). The overall functionality of the terminal is determined based on the status and function of the structures included in the Exposure Model within this shared area.

There is no data about the port capacity in terms of handling passengers and vehicles. Thus, the assumption is made that those are equal, as in the case of the Port of Orlivka (Danube Commission, 2022). The Port of Orlivka has a daily capacity of 700 vehicles (comprising 200 trucks and 500 cars) and 1,500 passengers.

Figure 19: Port of Isaccea – General view of the port and the designations of its terminal (source: Google Maps)

Table 7: Port of Isaccea – Port components relevant as business nodes for the port BOM

Business Node / Port Components	Model ID	Capacity
Terminal – passengers handling	0	1,500 passengers/day
Terminal – vehicles handling	1	700 vehicles/day (200 trucks + 500 cars)

Traffic Analysis (General)

The numbers of cross-border races, passengers, and vehicles for international transport during 2020-2023 are all presented in Table 8. As the table demonstrates, there has been a substantial increase in the number of passengers transported through the port since 2022 and on. Although there is no data on import/export values, plausible assumptions can be made considering the current regional political and military context, as shown in Table 8.

Table 8: Port of Isaccea – Number of cross-border races, vehicles, and passengers and import/export ratio during 2020-2023

Year	Cross-border races	Vehicles	Vehicles Import/Export	Passengers	Passengers Import/Export
2020	1,305	4,829	50% / 50%	5,000	50% / 50%
2021	4,776	60,625	50% / 50%	158,139	50% / 50%
2022	6,547	150,443	60% / 40%	444,931	60% / 40%
2023	6,770	166,685	60% / 40%	530,013	70% / 30%

Broader/Aggregated Categories of Products/Services for the Purposes of the BOM Analysis

For the BOM analysis, passengers and vehicles are considered the port's "product" categories and are further distinguished by import and export data, as shown in Table 9.

Table 9: Port of Isaccea – Categories, import/export status, and mapping to model identifiers

Services Category	Import/Export	Model Name	Model ID
Passengers	Import	Pass I	0
	Export	Pass E	2
Vehicles	Import	Veh I	1
	Export	Veh E	3

Port Operation Flowchart (general)

Figure 20 presents the general port operation flowchart for both passengers and vehicles.

Figure 20: Port of Isaccea – Port operation flowchart (general)

Port Operation Flowchart for Passengers and Vehicles

Figure 21 depicts the more specific port operation flowchart for both passengers and vehicles. There is no data indicating seasonality effect.

Figure 21: Port of Isaccea – Port operation flowchart / Handling of passengers and vehicles

Information About Past Incidents

Data on past incidents is unavailable.

7.1.5. Port of Galați Complex: “Bazinul Nou” (The New Basin Port)

Port Location

The port terminal “**Bazinul Nou**” (The New Basin Port) in Galați is situated approximately between km 145+650 and 147+200 along the Lower Danube, on the river’s left bank defined in the downstream direction (i.e., toward the Black Sea) (Danube Commission, 2025). Figure 22 illustrates the location and the area of the examined port.

Figure 22: New Basin Port (Galați) – Location and area (source: Google Maps)

Port Multimodal Access and Connectivity

The port’s **water-based access** features both **fluvial (IWW)** and **maritime (sea) connectivity**. The port can be accessed via barges, fluvial, and maritime vessels of 15,000 DWT (APDM Galați, 2025a).

The port’s **land-based access** includes both **local** and **national road** connections, as well as **railway connectivity**. The port road network is connected to the Galați local road network, as well as the national road network and highways, thus connecting with all European countries (APDM Galați, 2025a). With respect to the railway infrastructure, this includes both European (standard/normal) gauge and Russian (broad) gauge tracks. The latter ensures connectivity with the national railway networks of Moldova and Ukraine. The total railway track length is 6,474 meters. This is allocated as follows: (a) 1,717 meters for the reception and delivery of trains, (b) 4,257 meters for loading and unloading operations, and (c) 500 meters of wide gauge track specifically for handling CSI (Commonwealth of Independent States) wagons (i.e., basically wagons moving along the broad gauge track) (APDM Galați, 2025a). A dedicated locomotive is used for all wagon handling within the port. The railway tracks and the roads of the port are illustrated in Figure 23.

Port Facilities (Assets from Exposure Model [T4.2] and General Information)

The port sector was constructed during 1909 – 1923 (Union of Romanian Inland Ports, 2025). All of the facilities of the Port are illustrated in Figure 23.

Figure 23: New Basin Port (Galați) – All facilities, assets, and equipment (source: APDM Galați, 2025a)

The **PLOTO Exposure Model [T4.2]** for the port's facilities is presented in Figure 24 and includes the following infrastructure:

- a. Seven gantry cranes (from a category of such similar assets denoted as “Group E3”): Truss-tower steel structures, 40m high, built in 1969, with a handling capacity of 800-1500 tonnes/day depending on the types of goods.
- b. One gantry crane (from a category of such similar assets denoted as “Group E4”): Truss-tower steel structure, 49m high, built in 1981, with a handling capacity of 800-1500 tonnes/day depending on the types of goods.
- c. One gantry crane (from a category of such similar assets denoted as “Group E5”): Truss-tower steel structure, 40m high, built in 1962, and has a handling capacity of 600-1000 tonnes/day depending on the types of good.
- d. Two warehouses: Both warehouses are reinforced concrete structures, built in 1970, with concrete roof slabs.

Figure 24: New Basin Port (Galați) – The area of assets considered in PLOTO (source: Google Maps)

7.1.6. Port of Galați Complex: “Docuri Port” (The Docks Port)

Port Location

The port terminal “**Docuri Port**” (The Docks Port) in Galați is situated approximately between km 148.4 and 149 along the Lower Danube, on the river’s left bank, defined in the downstream direction (i.e., toward the Black Sea) (Danube Commission, 2025). The location and the area of the examined port is presented in Figure 25.

Figure 25: The Docks Port (Galați) – Location and area (source: Google Maps)

Port Multimodal Access and Connectivity

The port’s **water-based access** features both **fluvial (IWW)** and **maritime (sea) connectivity**. The port can be accessed via barges, fluvial, and maritime vessels of 8,000 DWT (APDM Galați web page, 2025b). Vessels of this size are considered relatively small to medium sized and are often called "coasters" or "mini bulk carriers". The capacity and draft of the vessels admitted to operation depend exclusively on the maximum depth of the Danube recorded at Bara Sulina (APDM Galați web page, 2025b).

The port’s **land-based access** includes both **local** and **national road** connections, as well as **railway connectivity**. The port road network is connected to the Galați local road network, as well as the national road network and highways, thus connecting with all European countries (APDM Galați web page, 2025b). With respect to the railway infrastructure, this includes both European (standard/normal) gauge and Russian (broad) gauge tracks. The latter ensures connectivity with the national railway networks of Moldova and Ukraine. The total railway track length is 2,619 meters. This is allocated as follows: (a) 1,313 meters for the reception and delivery of trains, (b) 1,206 meters for loading and unloading operations, and (c) 100 meters of wide gauge track specifically for handling CSI (Commonwealth of Independent States) wagons (i.e., basically wagons moving along the broad gauge track) (APDM Galați web page, 2025b). A dedicated locomotive is used for all wagon handling within the port. The railway tracks and the roads of the port are illustrated in Figure 27.

Port Facilities (Assets from Exposure Model [T4.2] and General Information)

The **PLOTO Exposure Model [T4.2]** for the port's facilities is presented in Figure 26 and includes the following infrastructure:

- a. Two floating cranes (denoted as E_Gal1 and E_Gal2): Truss-tower steel structures, 53m and 42m, build in 1980 and 1989, with a handling capacity of 2.500–3.500 and 1.500–2.500 tonnes/day depending on the types of good, respectively.

- b. Four gantry cranes (from a category of such similar assets denoted as “Group E4”): Truss-tower steel structure, 49m high, built in 1981, with a handling capacity of 800-1500 tonnes/day depending on the types of goods.
- c. Three gantry cranes (from a category of such similar assets denoted as “Group E5”): Truss-tower steel structure, 40m high, built in 1962, and has a handling capacity of 600-1000 tonnes/day depending on the types of goods.
- d. Two warehouses (denoted as w101255DOC and w101259DOC): These are single-storey steel portal-frame structures, 5m and 8m high, constructed in 2009 and 2011, respectively.

Figure 26: The Docks Port (Galați) – The exposure assets considered in PLOT0 (source: Google Maps)

There are also additional assets and equipment used within the developed product flowcharts, which are not part of the PLOT0 Exposure Model for T4.2, which include:

- e. Eight silos: of total storage capacity 30,000 tonnes to store grain/cereals.
- f. Eight silos elevator: Each silo has its own special elevator in order to load/unload the cereals into the silos.

The port has 12 berths with a length of 1440 meters, out of which a berth with a length of 130 meters is located in the port basin and is specialized in cereals (APDM Galați web page, 2025b). It must be noted that for cereals storage, there is also a historical building with storage capacity of 25,000 tonnes, built 1884-1891 (Puterea web page, 2025). All facilities of the Port are presented in Figure 27, while a general view of it is provided in Figure 28.

Figure 27: The Docks Port (Galați) – All facilities, assets, and equipment (source: APDM Galați, 2025b)

Figure 28: The Docks Port (Galați) – General view of the examined port (source: Google Maps)

7.1.7. Port of Galați Complex: Business operation of the complex

The cargo data provided covers both port sectors, New Basin and Docks. For the purposes of this deliverable, these two sectors are treated together as a single entity, referred to as the “Port of Galati Complex.” It should be noted, however, that other sectors, i.e., ports, exist in Galati, which are not included in this analysis.

Port General Operation

The port complex operates as a **freight handling port**, primarily handling a range of bulk materials, such as cereals, oil, steel products, iron ore, stone, timber, scrap, forage, cement, equipment, chemicals, and fertilizers.

Port Complex facilities considered in BOM

The groups of similar assets considered in the BOMs of the port complex are comprised of the assets located in the New Basin and Docks ports, already presented in the previous sub-sections. Additionally, there are some open space areas in the ports for storage of cargo, which are denoted as “terminals”.

In general, it must be noted that the port of Galați operates with a combination of public and private management. The Maritime Danube Ports Administration, a state-owned company with its head office in Galați, is responsible for the administration of the port's core infrastructure, specifically the land and berths. However, the operational aspects of the port are primarily handled by private operators who own and manage storage facilities (including both open storage areas and warehouses), various types of equipment, key port installations such as gantry cranes, mobile equipment consisting of forklifts and trucks, and all utilities. Private operators who own and manage storage facilities (including both open storage areas and warehouses), various types of equipment, key port installations such as gantry cranes, mobile equipment consisting of forklifts and trucks, and all utilities, primarily handle the operational aspects of the port. In addition to the standard warehousing and open storage, the port also features grain silos for storage and a floating dock for ship maintenance and repair services.

Table 10 lists all relevant Galați components identified as business nodes (i.e., groups of similar assets and equipment or open-space areas) for the BOMs through flowchart analysis.

Table 10: Port of Galați Complex – Port components relevant as business nodes for the port BOM

Groups of assets/equipment in BOMs	ID
Terminal 1 unloading area	0
Terminal 2 open-space area	1
Terminal 3 open-space area	2
Gantry cranes E1-E2 (floating cranes)	3
Gantry cranes E3-E5	4
Standard mobile cranes	5
Mobile cranes with claws	6
Special cereal elevator	7
Cereal silos (x8)	8
Warehouses 101255DOC, 101259DOC	9

Traffic Analysis: Annual Freight Data

Table 11 presents the freight data collected and analyzed within PLOT. The table gives the complete list of cargo products and their associated annual freight volumes (in tonnes) for the period 2019-2022.

Table 11: Port of Galați Complex – Cargo traffic data (tonnes) for years 2019-2022 per product

Product / Year	2019	2020	2021	2022
Cereals	298,175	207,453	340,132	326,420
Steel products	141,199	275,042	185,326	391,826
Coil	11,086	0	0	0
Scrap	61,423	123,687	180,105	187,240
Fertilizer	13,747	13,418	28,540	30,153
Stone	152,578	167,912	52,969	37,932
Salt	0	0	0	33,250
Timber	1	0	0	0
Iron ore	2,493	0	2,500	0
Forage	0	6,500	15,347	0
Cement	0	7,018	1,069	0
Equipment	3	0	0	0
Chemicals	0	0	6,566	0
Other	4,062	957	8,568	0
Oil	160,992	42,614	68,794	0
TOTAL	845,759	844,601	889,916	1,006,821

Traffic Analysis: Aggregated Categories of Cargo for the Purposes of the BOM Analysis

To simplify the analysis and avoid overly complex diagrams within the BOM analysis, the initial 6 product types were consolidated into five broader categories: Cereals, Steel, Scrap, Bulk Material, and Products. These categories are further distinguished by import and export data. The specific products within each category, along with corresponding import and export information, are detailed in Table 12.

Table 12: Port of Galați Complex – Product categories, associated products, import/export status, and model designations

Product Category	Products (both imported/exported)	Import/Export	Model Designation
Cereals	Cereals	Export	Cereals
Steel	Steel products, Coil	Export	Steel
Scrap	Scrap	Import	Scrap I
		Export	Scrap E
Bulk Material	Fertilizer (imported only), Stone, Salt, Timber, Iron ore, Forage, Cement	Import	Bulk I
		Export	Bulk E
Products	Oil, Equipment, Chemicals (import only), Other	Import	Prod I
		Export	Prod E

Traffic Analysis: Export/Import Distribution and Means of Transport Data

The distribution of freight volume by cargo flow type (import and export) per product type at the Galați port is presented in Table 13. These coefficients are consistent across all years from 2019 to 2022. This means that for a given total volume of a specific cargo type, the table allows to determine the respective import and export volumes.

Table 13: Port of Galați Complex – Annual distribution of import and export freight volumes by cargo type

Cargo Flow Type	Import	Export
Cereals	0	1

Cargo Flow Type	Import	Export
Steel	0	1
Scrap	0.38	0.62
Bulk Material & Products	0.11	0.89
Oil	0.4	0.6

Regarding the distribution of freight volumes at the Port of Galați by waterway transport mode (maritime and fluvial), several datasets were analyzed.

The first dataset presents the annual freight volumes (in tonnes) and the number of vessels using the port during the period 2019–2022, disaggregated by maritime and fluvial transport modes (Table 14). Based on these data, the annual distribution factors of freight volumes between maritime and fluvial transport were derived (Table 15).

Table 14: Port of Galați Complex – Traffic analysis, i.e. annual freight volume (in tonnes) and no. of ships (2019–2022)

Year	MARITIME		FLUVIAL		TOTAL	
	Freight (t)	No. vessels	Freight (t)	No. vessels	Freight (t)	No. vessels
2019	505,071	123	340,688	294	845,759	417
2020	540,679	136	303,922	253	844,601	389
2021	595,287	150	294,629	251	889,916	401
2022	625,812	158	381,009	388	1,006,821	546

Table 15: The Docks Port (Galați) – Annual distribution of cargo by waterway transport mode (2019–2022)

Cargo IWW mode	2019	2020	2021	2022	mean
Maritime	0.6	0.64	0.67	0.62	0.63
Fluvial	0.4	0.36	0.33	0.38	0.37

Table 16 presents the distribution of the imported and exported freight volumes between the maritime and fluvial modes, illustrating the relative importance of each mode for inbound and outbound trade.

Table 16: Port of Galați Complex – Annual distribution of imported/exported cargo by waterway transport mode (2019–2021)

Cargo Flow Type	Cargo IWW mode	2019	2020	2021	mean
Import	maritime	0.36	0.42	0.38	0.39
	fluvial	0.64	0.58	0.62	0.61
Export	maritime	0.72	0.86	0.71	0.76
	fluvial	0.28	0.14	0.29	0.24

Finally, Table 17 further analyzes the traffic composition, showing the percentage share of **exports**, **imports**, and **transit** within the maritime and fluvial transport modes for the same period.

Table 17: Port of Galați Complex – Analysis of maritime and fluvial traffic distribution at the port (2019–2022)

Year	MARITIME					FLUVIAL				
	Export	Import	Transit	Total	No. vessels	Export	Import	Transit	Total	No. vessels
2019	79%	21%	0	60%	29%	45%	21%	33%	40%	71%
2020	67%	33%	0	64%	35%	19%	40%	40%	36%	65%
2021	93%	7%	0	67%	37%	77%	16%	6%	33%	63%
2022	N/A	N/A	N/A	62%	29%	N/A	N/A	N/A	38%	71%

Port Operation Flowchart for Cereals

Cereal handling is exclusively concentrated between July and September, indicating a 100% seasonality effect. Based on the available data, cereals are exclusively exported from the port (not imported from or transited through). All incoming cereal shipments arrive by truck, with no use of railway transport. For outgoing shipments, cereals are loaded onto both maritime and fluvial vessels. The flowchart of cereals handling is illustrated in Figure 29.

Figure 29: Port of Galați Complex – Port operation flowchart / Handling of cereals

Port Operation Flowchart for Steel

“Steel” represents a broad category that includes steel products and coil. This group of products is exclusively exported from the port. In terms of inland transport, approximately 90% of the steel cargo is delivered to and dispatched from the terminal by rail, while the remaining 10% is transported by road. Handling operations are steady throughout the year, with no observable seasonality. The flowchart of steel handling is presented in Figure 30.

Figure 30: Port of Galați Complex – Port operation flowchart / Handling of steel

Port Operation Flowchart for Scrap

Scrap is both imported to and exported from the port. For inland transport, all scrap, whether import or export, is moved exclusively by truck. Imported scrap arrives solely via maritime vessels, while exported scrap is shipped using both maritime and fluvial transport. A clear seasonality is observed, with activity distributed as approximately 5% between November and March and 95% between April and October. Figure 31 illustrates the port operation flowchart for steel products.

Figure 31: Port of Galați Complex – Port operation flowchart / Handling of scrap

Port Operation Flowchart for Bulk Material & Products

“Bulk Materials” and “Products” constitute broader categories that include: (a) fertilizer (import only), stone, salt, timber, iron ore, forage, and cement; and (b) equipment, chemicals (import only), other goods, and oil, respectively. All listed items are both imported and exported, except for fertilizer and chemicals, which are exclusively imported. Some imported products are transferred through the port solely via waterway transport, meaning they arrive and depart by vessel without using inland routes (i.e., waterway transit). For simplicity, this case is not modelled as a separate product category; instead, imported goods are allocated within the import route according to the available data. In terms of inland transport, all products are moved equally by rail and road, except for timber, which is handled exclusively by train. For maritime shipment, all products are transported using both maritime and fluvial vessels. There is no seasonality effect.

All products follow the same routes of handling within the port. Figure 32, which depicts the port operation flowchart for Bulk Material, applies identically to all Products.

Figure 32: Port of Galați Complex – Port operation flowchart / Handling of bulk material

7.1.8. Port of Brăila Complex: “Port ROMANEL”

Port Location

The port terminal “**Port ROMANEL**” is situated approximately at kilometer 168+500 (Port Romanel Brăila, n.d.) (more precisely between km 168+050 and 168+400, (Danube Commission, 2025)) along the Lower Danube, on the river’s left bank defined in the downstream direction (i.e., toward the Black Sea) (Port Romanel Braila, n.d.; Danube Commission, 2025). The terminal could be considered as a part of a general larger port definition, Brăila. This is situated between km 168+300 and 170+875, along the Lower Danube, on the river’s left bank defined in the downstream direction (i.e., toward the Black Sea) (Port Romanel Braila, n.d.; Aries Shipping Agency, 2013). The location and the area (red colour) of the examined port are given in Figure 33.

Figure 33: Port ROMANEL (Brăila) – Location and area (red colour) (source: Google Maps)

Port Multimodal Access and Connectivity

The port’s **water-based access** features both **fluvial (IWW)** and **maritime (sea) connectivity**. Notably, the port’s facilities are designed to handle marine vessels operating up to a 7-meter sea gauge, utilizing a 100-meter vertical quay for operations (Port Romanel Braila, n.d).

The port’s **land-based access** includes **railway connections** and both **local** and **national road** connections. The port road network is connected to the city of Brăila local road network, as well as the national road network and highways, thus connecting with all European countries [12]. The railway

infrastructure includes a double track spanning 517 linear meters, capable of handling 16 wagons simultaneously over an eight-hour shift (Port Romanel Braila, n.d).

Port General Operation

The port is a **freight handling port**. It offers a wide range of **services**, such as: (a) unloading/loading goods from and to fluvial and maritime vessels, as well as fluvial barges, trucks and wagons, (b) storage of goods in warehouses or platforms (open-space areas), (c) maintenance and repair activities, and (d) general reception activities, such as package, palletization, bagging, and marking (Port Romanel Braila, n.d).

Based on the data received, the port handles a diverse range of **products**, including cereals, salt, forage, steel plates, coils, grit, timber, and agricultural machinery. There are additional products handled by the port that are not included in the available dataset (Port Romanel Braila, n.d). These include raw materials, logs, pit ballast materials, stone, wire in coils, bar steel, chemical bulk solid products, goods in pallets, and big bags. Furthermore, the port is the main loader of wood products in the Galați-Brăila market and operates continuously, 24 hours a day, 7 days a week (Port Romanel Braila, n.d).

Port Facilities (Assets from Exposure Model [T4.2] and General Information)

Figure 34 provides the general view of the port, its facilities (warehouses and office building), open-space storage area, two quay mobile gantry cranes, and the internal rail system.

Figure 34: Port ROMANEL (Brăila) – General view of the examined port (source: Google Maps)

The **PLOTO Exposure Model [T4.2]** for the port's facilities includes the following infrastructure:

- a. An office building for administrative and operational coordination.
- b. Two gantry cranes (denoted as E_Bra1 and E_Bra2): These cranes are mobile, moving on rail tracks along the quay wall. They constitute truss-tower steel structures, built/installed in 1998, 40m high, with a handling (loading/unloading vessels) capacity of 800 tonnes/day.
- c. Two warehouses (denoted as W_Bra1 and W_Bra2): These are both single-storey steel portal frame structures constructed in 2000 and 2001, both 5m height, and with storage area of 6,300m² and 5,300m² (total 11,600m², Port Romanel Braila, n.d). Based on the available data, their primary function is the storage of cereals; however, they also support the port's general logistics operations by accommodating other types of goods as needed.

Within the provided product flowchart, there is also an additional equipment category labeled as “mobile cranes” for the loading and unloading of both trucks and rail cars, as well as silos for cereals with special elevators attached to each one. None of these assets are part of the PLOTO Exposure Model. Regarding storage operations, apart from the two warehouses, cargo can be stored either on

the quay apron or elsewhere within the port’s operational area. Those two locations constitute two storage area components of the BOM, denoted as “Terminal 2” and “Storage”, respectively. Table 18 lists all relevant Brăila components identified as business nodes for the BOMs through flowchart analysis.

Table 18: Port ROMANEL (Brăila) – Port components relevant as business nodes for the port BOM

Business Node / Port Components	Model name
Terminal 1 – Location	Term 1
Terminal 2 – Open-space close to piers (storage area)	Term 2
Open-space storage area	Storage
Cereal Silos	Silos
Special Cereal Elevator	Elevator
Gantry Cranes	Gantry
Mobile Cranes (x8, max lifting capacity 25 t)	Mobile Crane
Warehouses	Ware
Business Node / Port Components	Model name

Traffic Analysis: Annual Freight Data

Table 19 presents the freight data collected and analyzed within PLOTO for the Port of ROMANEL in Brăila. The table gives the complete list of cargo products and their associated annual freight volumes (in tonnes) for the period 2019-2023. Analysis of this freight volume data reveals that the steel products category (steel plates and coil) constitutes the primary cargo handled by the port over the analyzed period.

Table 19: Port ROMANEL (Brăila) – Cargo traffic data (tonnes) for years 2019-2023 per product

Product / Year	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023
CEREALS	112,081	63,302	89,706	114,672	23,314
STEEL PLATES	151,894	128,032	136,052	134,468	168,188
COIL	93,658	108,624	150,583	117,099	78,757
SALT	705	0	0	19,486	14,416
GRIT	1,195	1,271	1,592	2,334	2,669
TIMBER	8,144	4,119	0	0	0
AGRICULTURAL MACHINERY	4	0	0	0	0
FORAGE	0	0	0	0	0
TOTAL	367,681	305,348	377,933	388,059	287,344

Traffic Analysis: Aggregated Categories of Cargo for the Purposes of the BOM Analysis

To simplify the analysis and avoid overly complex diagrams within the BOM analysis, the initial 6 product types were consolidated into four broader categories: Cereals, Steel Products, Timber, and Bulk Material. These categories are further distinguished by import and export data. The specific products within each category, along with corresponding import and export information, are detailed in Table 20. Agricultural machinery and forage were excluded from categorization due to zero freight volume during the analyzed period (Table 19).

Table 20: Port ROMANEL (Brăila) – Product categories, associated products, import/export status, and model designations

Product Category	Products (both imported/exported)	Import/Export	Model Designation
Cereals	Cereals	Export	Cereals
Steel Products	Coil, Steel Plates	Import	Steel I
		Export	Steel E
Timber	Timber	Import	Timber I
		Export	Timber E
Bulk Material	Salt, Grit	Import	Bulk I
		Export	Bulk E

Traffic Analysis: Export/Import Distribution and Means of Transport Data

The distribution of freight volume by cargo flow type (import and export) per product type at the Brăila port is presented in Table 21. These coefficients are consistent across all years from 2019 to 2023. This means that for a given total volume of a specific cargo type, the table allows to determine the respective import and export volumes.

Table 21: Port ROMANEL (Brăila) – Annual distribution of import and export freight volumes by cargo type (2019–2023)

Cargo Flow Type	Import	Export
Cereals	0	1
Steel Products	0,7	0,3
Timber	0,5	0,5
Bulk Material	0,5	0,5

The distribution of vessel traffic is 95% fluvial (primarily barges) and 5% maritime. As for the distribution of freight volume by transport mode (maritime and fluvial), the only available data was provided in the form of percentages of the aggregate freight volume, as shown in Table 22.

Table 22: Port ROMANEL (Brăila) – Distribution of freight volume by vessels type during the period 2019-2023

Transport Mode	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	mean
Maritime	0,38	0,18	0,4	0,26	0,33	0,31
Fluvial	0,62	0,82	0,6	0,74	0,67	0,69

However, detailed data on the distribution of the *import* and *export* freight volumes (either aggregate or per product) by transport mode (maritime and fluvial) is unavailable. Therefore, the known aggregate percentages of maritime vs. fluvial freight volume (Table 22) were applied to all products for both export and import. This distribution of freight volume is detailed in Table 23, which shows the annual and five-year mean percentage distribution of imports and exports by transport mode from 2019 to 2023. This data is used to select appropriate distribution factors in the BOMs for: a) product input and b) distribution from a business node to the maritime output and fluvial output business nodes.

Table 23: Brăila port – Distribution of import/export freight volume by transport mode during the period 2019-2023

Cargo Flow Type	Transport Mode	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	mean
Import (input from)	Maritime	0,38	0,18	0,4	0,26	0,33	0,31
Import (input from)	Fluvial	0,62	0,82	0,6	0,74	0,67	0,69
Export (output to)	Maritime	0,38	0,18	0,4	0,26	0,33	0,31
Export (output to)	Fluvial	0,62	0,82	0,6	0,74	0,67	0,69

Port Operation Flowchart for Cereals

Figure 35 depicts the port operation flowchart for cereals. Cereal handling is exclusively concentrated between July and September, indicating a 100% seasonality effect. Based on the available data, cereals are only exported from the port (not imported from or transited through). All incoming cereal arrives by truck, with no use of railway transport. For outgoing shipments, cereals are loaded onto both maritime and fluvial vessels.

Figure 35: Port ROMANEL (Brăila) – Port operation flowchart / Handling of cereals

Port Operation Flowchart for Steel Products

“Steel products” comprise a broad category that includes steel plates and coils. They are both imported to and exported from the port, with imports accounting approximately for the 70% and export for the 30% of the total category freight, respectively. In terms of inland transportation, the majority of steel products both arrive at and exit from the terminal by train (approximately 90%), with the remaining 10% transported by truck. Their handling activities remain constant throughout the year, showing no seasonality effects. According to the collected data, these products are stored in open spaces, either on the quay apron or elsewhere within the port’s operational area, indicating that no warehouse storage is involved. Figure 36 presents the port operation flowchart for steel products.

Figure 36: Brăila port – Port operation flowchart / Handling of steel products

Port Operation Flowchart for Timber

Timber is both imported to and exported from the port. Its transport is distributed between both maritime and fluvial vessels. In terms of inland transportation, timber both arrives at and exits from the terminal exclusively by train (100%). The handling of timber exhibits seasonality, with approximately 95% of operations taking place between April and October and only 5% occurring between November and March. The cargo is stored either in warehouses or in open space, typically in

front of the warehouse, and in both cases stacked on pallets. Figure 37 presents the port operation flowchart for timber.

Figure 37: Brăila port – Port operation flowchart / Handling of timber

Port Operation Flowchart for Bulk Material

“Bulk material” constitutes a broad category that includes salt and grit, both of which are imported to and exported from the port. Regarding inland transportation, truck (50%) and train (50%) move salt equally, while grit is transported exclusively by truck (100%). However, this distinction is not reflected in the BOM analysis, and for this reason, both products are aggregated under the broader “Bulk material” category. The handling of bulk materials shows no evidence of seasonality. Operations take place in two distinct ways: (a) bagged material is stored either in warehouses or in open-space areas, while (b) unbagged material is transferred directly between trucks/trains and vessels. Figure 38 depicts the port operation flowchart for bulk material.

Figure 38: Brăila port – Port operation flowchart / Handling of bulk material

Information About Past Incidents

No physical damage to warehouses due to physical hazards has been recorded. While historical data on the consequences of crane failures is unavailable, the port's operations are affected if one of the two floating cranes is out of service (e.g., due to failure or maintenance). Because each crane serves a specific area, a replacement floating crane is typically deployed. If a replacement is unavailable, the affected ship must be moved to another berth, requiring logistical reconfiguration and resulting in operational delays and increased ship costs.

7.2 Demonstration Case B: Hungary

The “**Port of Budapest**” on Csepel island is the largest trimodal port in Hungary. It is close to the centre of the national railway and road network. The M0 motorway is 8 km away to which the other Hungarian motorways connect. The main route of barges is between Budapest and the coastal ports at the Black Sea. The main directions of the railway traffic are Western Europe and the coastal ports in the North basin of the Adriatic Sea. The port’s location is presented in Figure 39.

Figure 39: Port of Budapest – Location

Figure 40 shows the port, the Soroksári marshaling yard, the railway between the yard and the port, and the waiting area for waterborne vehicles south of the port.

Figure 40: Port of Budapest – Layout of the port’s location and its connection to Danube and railway

The cargo trains are moved between the port and the Soroksári marshaling yard using shunting locomotives through the Gubacsi bridge, which is in a poor condition, and the speed limit is 5 km/h.

The bridge plays a crucial role in railway freight transport in Hungary because the port manages around 10 % of the total railway freight transport. Accordingly, the Hungarian state will renovate the bridge in the near future. An external company schedules shunting services in the morning and afternoon for container trains, and there are on-demand services using the port companies’ shunting locomotives. Unpropelled barges wait on the Danube south of the port. The port operator tows barges using their tugboats. The port has three dock basins from which the north basin is not used for freight transport; however, there is a RoRo terminal. Usually, hotel vessels park in the northern basin, and the police also use it. In the southern basin, only petroleum products are transported. In the PLOTO project, the focus was put on the middle basin. The main freight transport routes and annual volumes in 2023 are summarized in Table 24.

Table 24: Port of Budapest – Freight transport volumes at the port in 2023

From\To	Water	Railway	Road
Water	-	2 kt other bulk cereals 62 kt fertilizer 44 kt metal products	514 kt petroleum products
Railway	8 kt grain 24 kt other bulk cereals 43 kt coal 29 kt scrap metal 1450 TEU containers	73100 TEU containers	66 kt iron and metal products 107 600 TEU containers
Road	3.2 kt petroleum products 95 kt grain 5 kt scrap metal 2130 TEU containers	107 600 TEU containers	158 400 TEU containers

Regarding inland navigation in the middle basin, the typical goods are cereals, metal products, fertilizer, and coal. Grain is the most significant cereal. Other cereals are corn, barley, rapeseed, and sunflower seeds. The container transport is not significant, but there is a great potential to grow. Containers are usually transported on railways and by trucks at the port. Barge capacity can be fully exploited during water levels between 2.5 and 3.5 meters (at Budapest). While 75-80% of the capacity can be exploited during water levels of 1 m.

The key infrastructure is summarized in Figure 41.

Figure 41: Port of Budapest – Layout of key infrastructure groups

Basically, containers, cereals and fertilizers are handled on the north coast of the middle basin, while metal products and coal on the south coast. Railway tracks 1-7 are used for container transport exclusively, while tracks 8 – 10 are multipurpose, and can be used for container, cereal, and fertilizer transport. Regarding the area, the open-air container storage (ID 14) is the largest. Usually 4 – 5 thousand containers are stored there (most of them empty). Containers are loaded using reach stackers currently, but the deployment of rubber-tyred gantry cranes is planned to improve capacity. Container trucks are loaded at the east side of the container terminal (ID 15), where there is also a truck parking lot. Sometimes, the parking lot is crowded. Therefore, there is an initiative for truck scheduling which will optimise the arrival of trucks. Container barges are loaded with one gantry crane (ID 16), which may be replaced in 2025.

Cereals can be stored in silos (ID 17); however, cereals typically traverse through the port without storage. Accordingly, the typical utilization of the silos is between 20 and 50%. Silos can be loaded and unloaded on both sides; however, only trucks can use both sides. Cereals are loaded into barges using a roofed slide and a grain elevator (ID 18). The slide is operable during water levels below 3.5 meters. When the slide is not operable, the grain elevator is used, which is slower and more expensive. Fertilizers are stored in warehouses (ID 19), and loaded into barges using a slide, and unloaded using a gantry crane. Bulldozers are used to load and unload fertilizer warehouses.

Railway track 11 – 13 are used to transport metal products and coal. Metal products can be stored in a warehouse (ID 21) and open-air (ID 25 and 29). A roofed loading area (ID 22) belongs to the warehouse, where railways and barges can be loaded using a gantry crane. The open-air storage areas can be loaded and unloaded from/to trains using grab crawls (ID 23 and 24) and gantry cranes (ID 27 and 28). Coal is stored open-air at ID 26. Barges can be loaded with coal and metal products using gantry cranes ID 27 and 28. Coal and fertilizer loading infrastructure are interchangeable; however,

the transfer of goods from one terminal to the other has additional costs. Other infrastructure components are not replaceable.

The key loading functions and their capacities are summarized in Table 25. A workday is 13 hours long, between 7 AM and 8 PM.

Table 25: Port of Budapest – Loading function and capacity

Loading function	Capacity
Containers: between railway, truck and open-air storage	5 mins / container
Cereals: From truck and railway into warehouse	600 t / day (except for sunflower) 300 t / day (sunflower)
Cereals: To barge	1000 t / day (except for sunflower) 600 t / day (sunflower)
Cereals: From warehouse to railways and trucks	400 t / day (except for sunflower) 300 t / day (sunflower)
Fertilizer: warehouse from barge or railway	500 t / day
Fertilizer: truck from barge, railway, or warehouse	500 t / day
Fertilizer: Barge from truck	1000 t / day
Coal: from truck to railway	600 t / day
Coal: from railway to barge	600 t / day
Coal: from open-air storage to barge	1000 t / day
Coal: from open-air storage to railway or truck	500 t / day

7.3 Demonstration Case C: Belgium

In PLOTO Demonstration Case C, i.e., Belgium, there is no operating port and consequently a BOM was not developed.

8. Adaptation Strategies evaluation with "what-if" scenarios

8.1 Demonstration Case A: Romania

8.1.1. Targeted adaptation strategies development

The chapter on Demonstration Case A illustrates the process of developing targeted adaptation strategies based on impact analysis data, with examples focusing on port freight hubs. By simulating "what-if" scenarios of reduced functionality at a specific operational group, users can quantify the potential impacts. The chapter then demonstrates the application of proactive management tools to mitigate these impacts, providing a practical framework for implementing adaptation strategies.

8.1.1.1. Identification of critical port components via impact analysis

BOMs provide a framework within transportation and logistics networks for assessing the potential impact of disruptions on operations, particularly in terms of delay. In this section, analyses of BOMs using the Python-coded BCE are presented to support the development of targeted adaptation measures by examining "what-if" scenarios. These scenarios involve potential disruptions to key operational components, or "nodes," by simulating reduced functionality ratios, thereby identifying the critical components. This approach exemplifies the application of advanced analytical tools developed within the PLOTO framework with alternative input parameters to examine risk management and enhance system resilience across various sectors.

To demonstrate this methodology, simulations for all considered ports were conducted applying a 15% functionality to one node at a time within the port network. Importantly, each simulation focused on reducing the functionality of a single node, rather than applying the reduction to every node simultaneously. This approach allows for the isolation and analysis of the impact of disruptions at specific points within the port system. The value of 15% is entirely indicative, serving as an illustrative example and creating an idealized scenario for exploring the model's behaviour. Real-world disruptions vary significantly based on the specific event, affected infrastructure, and other contextual factors. The analyses also indicatively consider a 10-day disruption in July, a crucial detail given the seasonality of some handled products (accounted for in monthly data). These indicative parameters (15% reduction and 10-day July disruption) provide a useful basis for revealing nodes impacting product delays at Romanian ports, ultimately informing targeted adaptation measures.

The results of the BOM analysis of the 'what-if' scenarios of reduced node functionality, presenting only the summary of critical operational components (or "business nodes") and their corresponding products with delays are shown in Table 26 and Table 27, for the Romanian freight ports (i.e., Galați and Brăila) and passenger's ports (i.e., Isaccea, Sulina, and Tulcea), respectively. Ports not listed in the tables experienced no delays because of the reduced functionality scenarios.

Table 26: BOM analyses results of the 'what-if' scenarios at reduced node functionality (15% level) for the freight Romanian ports (Galați and Brăila). Summary of critical nodes and product delays

Port	Impacted Node	Impacted	Exported Freight	Exported Freight	Delay	Delay
	Name	Product	100% Functionality	15% Functionality	(Volume)	(Percentage)
	[-]	[-]	[tonnes]	[tonnes]	[tonnes]	[%]
Galați	Gantry 3-5	Steel	11,233.29	3,093.30	8,139.99	72.46
	Gantry 3-5	Scrap I	2,039.98	574.21	1,465.78	71.85
	Gantry 3-5	Scrap E	3,328.19	916.48	2,411.71	72.46

Port	Impacted Node Name	Impacted Product	Exported Freight 100% Functionality	Exported Freight 15% Functionality	Delay (Volume)	Delay (Percentage)
	[-]	[-]	[tonnes]	[tonnes]	[tonnes]	[%]
	Gantry 3-5	Bulk E	1,808.70	1,785.78	22.92	1.27
	Elevator	Cereals	36,485.33	13,387.50	23,097.83	63.31
Brăila	Term 2	Steel E	1,955.65	1,710.30	245.36	12.54
	Gantry	Steel I	4,588.69	3,908.20	680.49	14.83
	Gantry	Steel E	1,955.65	1,661.68	293.97	15.03
	Gantry	Bulk I	227.38	193.67	33.71	14.83
	Mobile Cranes	Steel I	4,588.69	3,649.26	939.43	20.47
	Mobile Cranes	Steel E	1,955.65	1,373.40	582.25	29.77
	Mobile Cranes	Bulk I	227.38	194.88	32.50	14.29

Table 27: BOM analyses results of the 'what-if' scenarios at reduced node functionality (15% level) for the passengers Romanian ports (Isaccea, Sulina, and Tulcea). Summary of critical nodes and product delays

Port	Impacted Node Name	Impacted Category	Movement 100% Functionality	Movement 15% Functionality	Delay	Delay (Percentage)
	[-]	[-]	[passengers]	[passengers]	[passengers]	[%]
Isaccea	TermPass	Pass I	9,931.67	1,568.44	8,363.23	84.21
	TermPass	Pass E	4,256.38	672.18	3,584.20	84.21
	TermVeh	Veh I	3,123.38	731.94	2,391.45	76.57
	TermVeh	Veh E	1,338.59	313.69	1,024.91	76.57
Tulcea	Term	Pass I	3,761.36	1,458.74	2,302.62	61.22
	Term	Pass E	3,941.89	1,528.76	2,413.14	61.22

8.1.1.2. Targeted adaptation strategies – Example for the Port of Galați

First off, conclusions from the BOM analyses are extracted: A) for the Port of Galați: delays primarily occur at Gantry 3-5 (for Steel, Scrap I, Scrap E, Bulk I, and Bulk E) and the Elevator (for Cereals), and B) for the port of Brăila: delays occur at Term 2 (for Steel I and Steel E), Gantry (for Cereals, Steel I, Steel E, Bulk I, and Bulk E), and Mobile Cranes (for Steel I, Steel E, and Bulk I).

With these in mind, the adaptation strategies will target these specific nodes and product flows. The description is provided for the 'what-if scenario' for the Port of Galați. Each proactive management tool has been provided based on the PIANC (2020) categories of measures.

A. Risk Sharing:

The data from the analysis of Galați port shows that potential damages to cereal elevators leading to reduced functionality of 15% results in significant delays for the product of cereals (63% delay ratio). These impact analysis results for 15% reduced functionality of cereal elevators at the Port of Galați, only for the product of cereals on the last day of the simulated scenario (day 10) are presented in Figure 42.

Input Diagrams

Port Model

Impact Analysis Results

Figure 42: Impact on cereal throughput at Galați port under 15% cereal elevator functionality (final simulation day)

In such a case, a significant opportunity for proactive risk management exists through a risk-sharing strategy between the ports of Brăila and Galați, specifically targeting the handling of cereals. Both ports process this commodity, making them ideal partners in a mutual support agreement.

Simulations with BOM confirm the feasibility of risk-sharing between the ports as a viable adaptation strategy. New analyses were conducted by redistributing 100% of the cereal volume overflow caused by a simulated 10-day period of 15% functionality at Galați cereal elevator from that port to the port of Brăila. The Galați simulation, with the reduced cereal volume, demonstrated that the port could manage the remaining throughput despite the elevator issue (Figure 43). Concurrently, a Brăila simulation, assuming full operational capacity and incorporating the additional volume from Galați, showed its ability to accommodate the increased freight without delays during the same 10-day period (Figure 44). The analysis for Brăila reveals that the freight volume of products handled by the port is much lower than its actual capacity in processing rate. Hence, even for significantly reduced functionality ratios of single business nodes at the port Galați, the port of Brăila is capable of receiving overflow cereals cargo.

This inter-port collaboration aligns with PIANC (2020) categories of measures, which, when specifically tailored for the Galați-Brăila risk-sharing scenario, *could* include the following:

- Social measures: i) Establishment of a formal information-sharing protocol between Galați and Brăila regarding cereal handling capacity, real-time operational status, and potential disruptions. This would enable rapid communication and coordinated responses during incidents at either port. ii) Development of joint contingency plans with local transportation providers servicing both Galați and Brăila to ensure seamless transfer of cereal cargo between the ports via alternative transport routes (rail, road, barge) when necessary. This focuses on logistical coordination between the two ports.
- Institutional measures: Formalization of a bilateral agreement between the port authorities of Galați and Brăila outlining the terms of the risk-sharing arrangement. This agreement should define responsibilities, communication protocols, cost-sharing mechanisms (if applicable), and

Figure 45: Impact on steel and scrap throughput at Galați port under 15% gantry cranes group E3-E5 functionality (final simulation day)

These delays clearly demonstrate the need for implementing the Risk Reduction and Control measures for this specific group of cranes. In accordance with the PIANC (2020) framework, such measures could include the following:

- Physical measures: i) Structural reinforcement, strengthening, or other protection or modification of the gantry group to withstand events such as extreme weather (high winds, heavy snow/ice) or earthquakes. This may involve material upgrades or improved structural connections. ii) Implementation of a rigorous preventive maintenance program for Gantry 3-5, with a focus on critical components. This includes regular inspections and component replacement. iii) Installation of a real-time monitoring system with sensors for early detection of potential problems and proactive intervention.
- Social measures: Advanced training for gantry operators to improve efficiency and the ability to handle unexpected situations. This can contribute to downtime redundancy.
- Institutional measures: Implementation of "build-back-better" policies for any repairs or replacements of port infrastructure. This ensures that infrastructure is rebuilt to a higher standard of resilience.

Implementation of these measures can lead to a decrease in damage susceptibility. Consequently, for the same disruptive occurrence that previously resulted in 15% functionality, higher functionality levels and reduced downtime may be achieved. While the cost of component reinforcement and other improvements is a significant factor, the goal is to reach an acceptable level of resilience that balances cost-effectiveness with operational continuity. Simulations conducted with the BCE demonstrate that if these measures are implemented to achieve 50% functionality for the same disruptive occurrence and for the same period of 10 days of downtime, a reduction in delays from 70% to 9% for the affected products can be realized. These results are illustrated on Figure 46 and presented in Table 28.

Figure 46: Impact on steel and scrap throughput at Galați port under 50% gantry cranes group E3-E5 functionality (final simulation day)

Table 28: Impact on exported freight at Galați port with 50% functionality of the group of gantry cranes E3-E5 after 10 days

Port	Impacted Node Name [-]	Impacted Product [-]	Exported Freight 100% Functionality [tonnes]	Exported Freight 15% Functionality [tonnes]	Delay (Volume) [tonnes]	Delay (Percentage) [%]
Galați	Gantry 3-5	Steel	11,233.29	10,117.92	1,055.37	9.39%
	Gantry 3-5	Scrap I	2,039.98	1,849.79	190.20	9.32%
	Gantry 3-5	Scrap E	3,328.19	3,015.51	312.68	9.39%
	Gantry 3-5	Bulk E	1,808.70	1,787.49	21.21	1.17%

C. Risk Consequences Abatement:

Recognizing that some level of disruption is unavoidable, even with robust risk reduction measures, a key aspect of proactive management is mitigating the consequences of such events. For the port of Galați, a critical strategy to minimize the downtime and the significant delay related to gantry crane damage is the establishment of a rapid crane replacement plan. This involves pre-arranged agreements with external crane providers for immediate deployment of a replacement crane in case of major damage or extended maintenance.

This strategy might involve measure in accordance with the PIANC (2020) framework, such as the following:

- Social: This includes preparing and raising awareness of contingency and emergency response plans among port staff, stakeholders, and local communities through regular drills and training exercises. Establishing agreements with external crane providers involves "liaising and coordinating with utilities and other service providers" and developing "information-sharing protocols" (PIANC, 2020). This ensures access to necessary resources (in this case, a replacement crane) during emergencies and involves "preparing and raising awareness of contingency,

emergency or disaster response plans" within the port organization, including training port personnel on activating the crane replacement plan and coordinating with the external provider.

- Institutional: Establishing a contingency or disaster response fund to provide financial resources to support rapid response and recovery efforts.

To demonstrate the effectiveness of this measure, simulations were conducted using the business model. The analysis process involved the following steps: First, a 15% reduction in functionality at Gantry Cranes E3-E5 was simulated, representing a partial damage event, and the resulting delays were calculated for a 10-day period. Second, the period required for the replacing crane's deployment (1, 2, or 3 days) was considered. During this deployment time, the original, partially functional (15%) gantry continued operation, and the resulting delays were calculated; these delays are unavoidable and represent the initial impact before the new crane becomes operational. Third, once the replacement crane was deployed, its operation was simulated for the remaining downtime period (10 days minus the deployment time), and the delay resulting from the new crane's operation (with a given capacity of 600 or 750 tonnes/day) was calculated. Finally, the total delay was calculated by summing the delay incurred during the deployment period (by the original, partially functional crane) and the delay incurred by the new crane during its operational period. The delay reduction percentage was then calculated by comparing the total delay with the initial delay observed with only the 15% functional gantry. The results are presented in Table 29.

Table 29: Reduction in delays at Galați port achieved by replacement gantry cranes with varying capacity and deployment time based on simulation results

New Gantry Capacity [tonnes/day]	Deployment Time [day]	Steel		Scrap I		Scrap E	
		Delay [tonnes]	Reduction [%]	Delay [tonnes]	Reduction [%]	Delay [tonnes]	Reduction [%]
Initial Delays		8,140.0	[-]	1,465.80	[-]	2,411.7	[-]
600	1	4,785.2	41.2	850.0	42.0	1,417.8	41.2
	2	5,179.5	36.4	921.6	37.1	1,534.6	36.4
	3	5,572.1	31.5	992.9	32.3	1,650.9	31.5
750	1	3,900.0	52.1	690.8	52.9	1,155.5	52.1
	2	4,395.2	46.0	780.7	46.7	1,302.2	46.0
	3	4,888.7	39.9	870.3	40.6	1,448.4	39.9

8.1.2. Scenario-based evaluation of Risk Transfer

Introduction: This section presents a comparative analysis of two BCSs (BCS0 - no insurance, and BCS2 - with insurance) in the aftermath of a severe flood affecting Galați Port. The goal is to assess how the availability of insurance influences recovery time and overall delays.

Scenario 1: No Insurance (Baseline - BCS0): In a baseline scenario (BCS0) with no insurance, the port experiences a conceptual flooding event, resulting in significant damage to critical infrastructure, including gantry cranes and cereal elevators. The absence of insurance coverage leads to a lack of immediate funds for repairs, severely impacting BC. Recovery relies on standard repair procedures and available financial resources, leading to prolonged downtime and supply chain disruptions. A conceptual recovery timeline for this scenario without insurance (BCS0) is given in Table 30.

Table 30: Conceptual example for BCS0 and BCS2 comparison – Recovery timeline without insurance (BCS0)

Time (Days)	Event / Status	Functionality	
		Gantry Cranes E3-E5	Cereal Elevators
Day 0	Flood event occurs	0%	0%
Day 1- 10	Floodwaters recede	0%	0%
Day 11-30	Debris cleanup, damage assessment	0%	0%
Day 31	Port reopens, but assets inoperable	33%	38%
Day 45	Assets repaired	53%	63%
Day 60	Assets repaired	80%	88%
Day 75	Assets repaired	93%	100%
Day 90	Ports restore full functionality	100%	100%

Scenario 2: Parametric (Non-Indemnity, Index-Based) Insurance (BCS2): The same extreme flooding event occurs. The port has a parametric insurance contract in place, which triggers an immediate payout once water levels exceed a predefined threshold. Immediate financial support enables faster recovery, allowing for early debris removal and expedited repair of critical infrastructure. A conceptual recovery timeline for this scenario with parametric insurance (BCS2) is given in Table 31.

Table 31: Conceptual example for BCS0 and BCS2 comparison – Recovery timeline with parametric insurance (BCS2)

Time (Days)	Event / Status	Functionality	
		Gantry Cranes E3-E5	Cereal Elevators
Day 0	Flood event occurs	0%	0%
Day 6	Insurance payout received	0%	0%
Day 1- 10	Floodwaters recede	0%	0%
Day 11-20	Debris cleanup, damage assessment	0%	0%
Day 21	Port reopens, but assets inoperable	33%	38%
Day 30	Assets repaired	53%	63%
Day 40	Assets repaired	80%	88%
Day 45	Assets repaired	93%	100%
Day 50	Ports restore full functionality	100%	100%

Methodology and Results Comparison: Freight handling capabilities were analyzed using the BCE, simulating two scenarios (insured and uninsured) at critical recovery points: 50- and 90-days post-event. The impact of insurance on recovery was assessed by analyzing delayed freight volume and percentages at these timeframes. Table 32 presents the delayed freight volume results for both scenarios. Figure 47 and Figure 48 illustrate these delays after 50 days for the uninsured scenario (BCS0) and the insured scenario (BCS2), respectively.

Key findings reveal that insurance enables a significantly faster recovery. At 50 days, the insured scenario (BCS2) drastically reduces delays compared to the uninsured scenario (BCS0); for example, steel delays at 50 days drop from 73.3% in BCS0 to 37.6% in BCS2. While BCS2 achieves zero delays by 90 days, BCS0 still experiences delays, reaching as high as 21.9% for steel and scrap. Furthermore, BCS0 suffers substantial economic losses due to export delays, resulting in supply chain disruptions and increased storage costs. Conversely, BCS2 minimizes these losses by providing rapid access to funds for repairs. Finally, insurance enables the port to operate at a higher capacity earlier, lessening the burden on alternative ports and mitigating regional economic repercussions.

Table 32: Conceptual example for BCS0 and BCS2 comparison – Results and comparison of delay of freight volume and percentage for BCS0 and BCS2 at 50- and 90-days post-event

Product	BCS0		BCS2		BCS0		BCS2	
	Delay [tonnes]	Delay [%]						
Cereals	107.813,3	58,6	11.963,32	6,5	0,00	0,0	0	0
Steel	41.562,2	73,3	21.306,48	37,6	22.597,19	21,9	0	0
Scrap Imports	7.516,5	73,0	3.869,94	37,6	4.111,21	21,9	0	0
Scrap Exports	12.314,0	73,3	6.312,67	37,6	6.695,08	21,9	0	0

Figure 47: Impact on cereals, steel, and scrap throughput at Galați after 50 days of simulated conceptual flood event damages to gantry cranes and cereal elevators. Simulation carried out under recovery without enhancement from insurance (no insurance - BCS0) (final simulation day)

Figure 48: Impact on cereals, steel, and scrap throughput at Galați after 50 days of simulated conceptual flood event damages to gantry cranes and cereal elevators. Simulation carried out under recovery enhanced with parametric insurance (BCS2) (final simulation day)

8.2 Demonstration Case B: Hungary

8.2.1. Hazards

We summarized the hazardous weather conditions with their occurrence and probability categories in Table 33. The temperature, precipitation, and wind speed data source was Weatherspark (2025), and the source of water level data was Hydroinfo (2025).

Table 33: Port of Budapest – Environmental hazards

ID	Environmental condition	Typical occurrence
H1	Heavy rain	Summer, 10 - 20 days
H2	Prolonged sub-zero temperature	January and February, few days
H3	Water level below 1 m	Summer and Autumn, 10 – 25 days
H4	Water level between 1 and 1.5 m	Summer and Autumn, 30 – 40 days
H5	Water level between 4 and 6.5 m	30 – 50 days
H6	Water level between 6.5 and 9 m	Couple of days in every 3 – 4 years
H7	Wind (gust) speed above 40 km/h	Spring and Summer, 30 – 40 days
ID	Environmental condition	Typical occurrence

Prolonged sub-zero temperatures are getting less and less frequent due to global warming. However, sub-zero temperatures are typical at the Budapest port; prolonged periods are not typical. Icing in bays is unusual and hasn't occurred in the last 15 years. Water levels below 1 m are becoming more likely due to CC. Typically, the days when the water level is below 1 m are between 10 and 25 per year. However, there are years when it does not occur (e.g., 2020 and 2024) and extremely dry years when it is much longer (79 days in 2019). Moreover, low water levels are likely during autumn, not just summer. Water levels between 4 and 6.5 meters are frequent, but the seasonal trends are disappearing due to CC. Heavy rainfall in catchment areas is becoming less predictable and may occur at almost any time of the year. Since 2013, the water level was four times higher than 6.5 meters: twice in June, and one occasion in September and December. Heavy wind can occur almost any time of the year, but is more typical during spring and summer.

8.2.2. Targeted adaptation strategies development

We assessed the impact of each hazard on key functions and infrastructure. Those are presented in Table 34.

Table 34: Port of Budapest – Hazard impact on key functions and infrastructure

Hazard	Key functions & infrastructure	Redundancy	Vulnerability	Recoverability	Preparedness	Reactiveness
H1	Loading cereals and fertilizer	None	Medium	Fast	Medium	Good
H2	Loading coal	None	Medium	Medium	Medium	Good
H3	Waterborne transport	Railway, Road	High	Slow	Low	-
H4	Waterborne transport	Railway, Road	Low-Medium	Slow	Medium	Good

Hazard	Key functions & infrastructure	Redundancy	Vulnerability	Recoverability	Preparedness	Reactiveness
H5	Waterborne transport	Railway, Road	Low-Medium	Slow	Medium	Good
H6	Waterborne transport	Railway, Road	High	Slow	Low	-
H6	Port infrastructure	None	Low	Fast	Good	Good
H6	Track 1, 2	Track 3-7	High	Medium	Medium	Good
H7	Craning	None	High	Fast	Good	Good
H7	Container storing	None	Medium	Medium	Medium	Good
H7	Reach stackers: cont. handling	None	High	Fast	Medium	Good

Heavy rain extends loading time, block slides, and cause loss of cereals and fertilizer. Cereals and fertilizer can be loaded from and into barges under a roof, but the loading of railway cars is done in the open air. There is no redundancy, but the recoverability is fast: as soon as the intensity of rain decreases. The preparedness of the port is medium because, on the one hand, the weather forecast is frequently monitored, but on the other hand, loading areas are not entirely roofed. Reactiveness is good because the reactions are fast and well-known among the workers. Prolonged sub-zero temperature coal may start building up, hardening the handling, and some of the coal may stick to the railway cars. Accordingly, the vulnerability is medium, and the performance recovers when the low temperatures end. The preparedness is good because the forecast is monitored, and the loading is managed accordingly, but anti-freeze agents or vibrators are not used. Reactiveness is good because the prolonged loading times are calculated.

A port's vulnerability to fluctuating water levels stems from the characteristics of the waterway. Thus, key mitigation measures are not the port's exclusive responsibility. In this paper, the responsibilities were not analyzed, only the impacts and the missing measures. Water levels below 1 m significantly impact inland navigation, making waterborne transportation impossible. Accordingly, the vulnerability is high, and the recoverability is slow because of the significant impact on the freight chains. The preparedness is low despite regular monitoring and reliable water level forecasts. Although the solution to inland navigability would be water control, established cooperation with the railway and road sector would help mitigate droughts' effects. Since there are no significant mitigation measures, the reactiveness is not assessed. During water levels between 1 and 1.5 m barges, maximum weight capacity cannot be exploited, reducing the economy of heavy goods transportation. The recoverability is slow due to the impact on the freight chain. Better cooperation with other transportation modes would help to mitigate the effects. Reactiveness is good because barges are loaded according to the forecasted water levels. High water levels (H5 and H6) impact inland navigation similarly to low water levels. The maximum capacity of barges may not be exploited because of maximum height restrictions or because entire sections are blocked. The preparedness for water levels between 4 and 6.5 m is medium because the limitations are identified, and the reactiveness is good because the measures are well-known among the workers. The vulnerability to water levels between 6.5 and 9 m is high for

waterborne transport but good for the port infrastructure. There is an established mobile dam infrastructure, and most of the port area is above the highest water level in the last 200 years. Although mobile dams can be dismantled quickly and the operation can return to normal, sanitization of the port infrastructure and dredging may be necessary. Preparedness and reactivity are similar: the port infrastructure measures are complete and well known. Finally, water levels between 6.5 and 9 m reduce the bearing capacity, limiting the utilization of tracks 1 and 2. The vulnerability is high, but the recoverability is fast: as soon as the water level is below 6 m. The preparedness is medium because there are redundancy tracks, but the port walls may be improved. Reactiveness is good because the measures are well known.

Craning must be stopped during gust wind speed over 40 km/h. The recoverability is fast because craning can continue when the wind intensity decreases. Wind speeds are monitored regularly, and employees are alerted in time (good reactivity). Heavy wind also affects container storage because it may overturn containers. Therefore, if necessary, containers are re-arranged in a way that is more resilient to heavy wind. However, static windbreakers could also reduce vulnerability (medium preparedness). Finally, the operation of reach stackers must also be stopped during heavy wind because of the danger of overturning containers.

The limited functionality of the port due to heavy wind and rain can impact on the flow of trucks, leading to an overcrowded parking lot. Besides reducing the capacity degradation of functionality during such weather conditions, the parking of trucks can also be supported by intelligent information services:

- Classification and parking management of trucks based on the characteristics of the operation to minimise the time spent at the intermodal hub. Namely, trucks are called in an order that helps to minimise the operational movements. For example, trucks that deliver the containers stored at the top are called first, and then trucks delivering containers stored at the bottom are called last.
- Time slot booking to alleviate the peak-time load: the capacity is determined for periods, and delivery companies can book their slots. Vehicles arriving on time are called first to reduce waiting time and encourage the use of booking services. Accordingly, the workload fluctuation decreases, and capacity can be better managed and exploited.

In summary, the reactivity at the port is good because the available measures are applied quickly and appropriately. Considering the freight volumes, the port is most exposed to water level changes, which will intensify due to CC. The solution is the water level control along the Danube. Until then, better cooperation among freight companies may help temporarily replace waterborne transport. Other hazard occurrences do not hinder the increase of freight transport soon; however, some measures may help to mitigate the impacts, such as extending the roof over cereal and fertilizer loading bays, anti-freeze agents for coal loading, improving the bearing capacity of tracks 1 and 2 during high water level, windbreakers around the container storage area, and intelligent parking management solutions for trucks.

9. Conclusions

This report constitutes one of the deliverables of **WP6** denoted as **D6.3 “Business Continuity Models, Adaptation Strategies Standard Response Procedures”**, and related to tasks: **T6.2 “Assessing Business Continuity Models and Adaptation Strategies”** and **T6.3 “Assessing response actions and establishing Standard Response Procedures”**.

The deliverable addresses the increasing frequency and intensity of extreme events, amplified by **CC**, which call for coordinated, evidence-based, and adaptive management mechanisms to protect **IWW ports**. It proposes a **multi-layered resilience framework** where: (i) **SRPs/SOPs** secure immediate response and stabilization (“emergency phase”), (ii) **Adaptation Strategies** ensure adjustment and improvement of systems (“recovery phase”), and (iii) **BCSs** provide continuity and financial resilience (“post-event sustainability phase”). These components **collectively form a holistic and replicable framework** enabling the mitigation of cascading failures, reduction of downtime, and maintenance of essential port functions under adverse conditions.

Operational outputs of the deliverable include: (i) hazard-specific **SRPs/SOPs** developed through end-user engagement and data collection, (ii) **activation thresholds** for SOPs defined using port-specific indicators, (iii) **Adaptation Strategies** categorized into proactive and reactive measures, with the later detailed through techniques including risk avoidance, sharing, reduction, abatement, and transfer, and (iv) **BCSs** formulated as sector-wide mechanisms designed to maintain or restore operational and economic functionality following disruptions.

D6.3 also provides the **analytical basis within one of the Indirect Impact Assessment tools** developed in PLOTO. Specifically, the **BOMs** which were implemented in the **BCE** for the ports of Demonstration Case A (Romania, Lower Danube), allowing the quantification of indirect impacts, operational performance under disruption, and recovery potential.

The primary objective of D6.3 was to leverage the **BCE/BOMs** to evaluate the effectiveness of response and recovery actions under simulated disaster scenarios. The **“What-if” simulations** demonstrated how alternative operational decisions, such as cargo rerouting, resource reallocation, or activation of contingency nodes, affect port performance and BC. The simulations provided evidence for the comparative effectiveness of different BCSs and adaptation measures. Moreover, by deploying a series of “what-if” simulations, the project has demonstrated how **data-driven decision support tools** can quantify hazard impacts, assess the effectiveness of mitigation measures, and inform proactive policy design for ports and related infrastructures.

Overall, D6.3 provides a solid foundation for **operational resilience** in the IWW ports. By combining technological innovation (BOMs/BCE), structured procedural frameworks (SRPs/SOPs, Adaptation Strategies, and BCSs), and participatory end-user engagement, the deliverable supports policy development, strategic planning, and practical implementation. The outcomes ensure that inland ports remain **functional, adaptive, and economically viable** under evolving environmental, operational, and climatic pressures, contributing to the establishment of a coherent European framework for port resilience and BC.

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